

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI TRIESTE

Dipartimento di Fisica

CORSO DI LAUREA MAGISTRALE
INTERATENEO IN FISICA

Curriculum Fisica nucleare e subnucleare

TESI DI LAUREA MAGISTRALE

Particle identification by Cherenkov
imaging techniques in the experiment
ePIC at EIC

Laureando:

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Relatrice:

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Dott. Bressan Andrea

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Summary

This thesis is dedicated to report the original simulation studies performed by the student for the optimization of the particle identification counter dRICH (dual radiator Ring Imaging Cherenkov) for the ePIC experiment at the Electron Ion Collider (EIC) under construction at the Brookhaven National Laboratory in USA.

The EIC project and its physics scope are introduced in Chapter 1. A sector of the physics scope, namely the nucleon transverse momentum dependent distributions is presented in Chapter 2. This particular scientific domain has been selected because its experimental study requires the Cherenkov imaging device dRICH, which is the main topic of this thesis. The ePIC experiment at EIC is described in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 introduces the principle of the Cherenkov imaging technics and illustrates the dRICH.

Chapter 5 presents a description of the ePIC software stack, which includes simulation, detector description and data reconstruction by up-to-date software technologies. The student became familiar with the whole stack of this complex software environment, also being able to add contributions by himself for implementations requested by his own studies.

The original work performed by the student is presented in Chapters 6, 7, 8 and 9, where the simulation studies are reported; they are dedicated to:

- the dRICH performance using Silicon PhotoMultipliers (SiPM) with different characteristics;
- the dRICH performance using mirrors with different parameters;
- establishing the dRICH time response and, therefore, the impact of the SiPM dark count rates;
- establishing the lower limit of the momentum range for effective particle identification with the dRICH.

The results reported in this thesis are summarized in Chapter 10.

Sommario

Questa tesi e' dedicata a relazionare il lavoro originale di studio con tecniche di simulazione svolto dal laureando per contribuire all'ottimizzazione del rivelatore dRICH (dual radiator Ring Imaging CHERenkov) che identifica le particelle nell'esperimento ePIC all'Electron Ion Collider (EIC), collisore in fase di costruzione a Brookhaven National Laboratory in USA.

Il progetto EIC e il suo ambito di fisica sono introdotti nel capitolo 1. Un settore dell'ambito di fisica e precisamente le distribuzioni relative ai nucleoni dipendenti dall'impulso trasverso sono presentate nel Capitolo 2. Questo particolare campo di fisica e' stato scelto perche' il suo studio sperimentale necessita del rivelatore Cerenkov ad immagine dRICH e tale rivelatore e' l'argomento centrale di questa tesi. L'esperimento ePIC a EIC e' descritto nel Capitolo 3. Il Capitolo 4 introduce il principio della tecnica Cerenkov a immagine e descrive il dRICH.

Il capitolo 5 presenta una descrizione dell'intero corredo di software dell'esperimento ePIC, che include la simulazione degli eventi, la descrizione dell'apparato sperimentale e la ricostruzione dei dati realizzati con tecnologie pienamente aggiornate. Il laureando ha familiarizzato con l'intero corredo di questo software complesso, ed ha potuto egli stesso contribuire con sviluppi specifici richiesti dai suoi propri studi.

Il lavoro originale del laureando e' presentato nei capitoli 6, 7, 8 e 9, in cui sono riportati gli studi di simulazione dedicati a:

- le prestazioni del dRICH usando Silicon PhotoMultiplier (SiPM) con differenti caratteristiche;
- le prestazioni del dRICH usando specchi con differenti parametri;
- la determinazione della risposta temporale del dRICH e, pertanto, l'impatto del rumore di fondo dei SiPM;
- ricavando il limite inferiore dell'intervallo di impulso in cui il dRICH e' efficace per l'identificazione delle particelle.

I risultati presentati in questa tesi sono riassunti nel Capitolo 10.

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Chapter 1

The Electron-Ion Collider

The Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) is an approved project in the USA [1]. The project includes the collider and the ePIC experiment (Chapter 3).

The collider is a complex of particle accelerators with unprecedented characteristics and parameters. It is the first electron-ion collider ever built. In the past, at the HERA collider at DESY, Germany, which ended operations in 2007, electron beams collided only with proton beams. The key parameters of the EIC are: luminosity up to $10^{34} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in e-p scattering, largely increased by 2-3 orders of magnitude with respect to HERA luminosity, a variable centre of mass energy (\sqrt{s}) between 21-141 GeV/ c^2 , highly polarized e-p scattering (70% polarization) and e-A scattering with a large variety of ions from hydrogen to uranium. A schematic overview of the EIC Collider is provided in Fig. 1.1.

The project was approved in 2019; currently, the collider and detector designs are being finalized. The start of the construction phase is expected in 2027, and its completion is scheduled during the early years of the 2030s. The collider is being realized at the Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL), Upton, New-York, U.S.A, where the RHIC collider is located.

RHIC is an ion-ion collider and, as such, it provides most of the civil engineering required for the EIC, including the tunnel and most components of the ion acceleration and storage ring, as well as the entire complex of polarized proton sources and the acceleration chain compatible with polarized ions. RHIC ended operations in February 2026 to allow for the significant modifications needed to integrate its components into the EIC. The electron complex, including the polarized source, acceleration chain, and storage ring, is new and will be constructed in the coming years.

The collider lattice allows for two interaction points: one will host the ePIC detector, included in the EIC project, while the second may be instrumented at a later stage.

Figure 1.1: The schematic overview of the EIC Collider; the yellow ring is the ion accelerating and storage ring; the red ring is the electron storage ring. The ion and electron acceleration and injection complexes are also shown. The two interaction regions are indicated; the location of the ePIC detector is marked (courtesy of BNL Media & Communications).

The EIC scientific scope is to address some of the most fundamental open questions related to QCD and hadronic matter[2]. The scope is organized around five pillars in hadron and nuclear physics:

1. **Nucleon spin investigation** - How do quarks, gluons, and orbital angular momentum contribute to proton spin? Spin is a fundamental property of matter. All elementary particles but Higgs carry spin. The Spin of composite particles, such as the proton, cannot be explained by a static picture, but is caused by the interplay of properties and interactions of quarks and gluons inside.

2. **Origin of the nucleon mass** - Does the mass of visible matter emerge from quark-gluon interactions? It is well known that the dynamics of the interactions can generate the mass. For instance, in atoms, Binding/Mass = 0.00000001; in nuclei, Binding/Mass = 0.01. In nucleons, this ratio is dramatic: Binding/Mass = 100, making the nucleon a true example of an energy cluster confined in an extremely limited space ($O(1 \text{ fm})$). The EIC will determine an important term contributing to the proton mass, the so-called QCD trace anomaly.
3. **3D imaging of the nucleons and the nuclei** - How are quarks and gluons distributed in space and momentum inside the nucleon and nuclei? How do the nucleon properties emerge from them and their interactions? How can we understand their dynamical origin in QCD? What is the relation to confinement?
4. **QCD in nuclei** - How do the confined hadronic states emerge from quarks and gluons? Is the structure of a free and bound nucleon the same? How do quarks and gluons interact with a nuclear medium? How do the quark-gluon interactions create nuclear binding?
5. **Dense gluon systems** - Does gluon density in nuclei saturate at high energy? How many gluons can fit in a proton? How does a dense nuclear environment affect the quarks and gluons, their correlations and interactions?

Clearly, to achieve these physics benchmarks, the ePIC experiment at EIC has to navigate a kinematic phase-space wider than the one explored so far and offer largely improved precision thanks to high luminosity. These features allow for an important overlap with past experiments and pave the way into unexplored phase-space of QCD (figure 1.2). Furthermore, the extraction of information in the low- x region is possible thanks to the energy domain; therefore, it provides critical information about the gluon-dominated regime and the high- x region, thanks to the high luminosity. The kinematic variables x and Q^2 are defined in Chapter 2. The wide scope also requires different experimental approaches. Nucleons and nuclei are investigated with a lepton probe, namely the electron, in Deep Inelastic Scattering (DIS). The various physics domains are assessed by detecting in the final state only the scattered lepton (inclusive DIS), detecting also hadrons present in the final state (semi-inclusive DIS), or detecting all the particles in the final state in selected processes (exclusive measurements). In Chapter 2, the basic concepts of QCD are introduced as a framework to describe the physics processes that can be addressed by semi-inclusive DIS.

In a collider experiment, pseudorapidity (η) is generally considered a commonly used spatial coordinate representing the angle (θ) of a particle relative to the beam

Figure 1.2: x - Q^2 kinematics covered by EIC (Yellow) of $e+p$ (left hand plot) and $e+A$ collision (right hand plot). The blue region demonstrates the coverage of existing measurements from lepton nucleon scattering at CERN, DESY, JLab and SLAC along with polarized $p+p$ scattering at RHIC.

Figure 1.3: Schematic showing the distribution of the scattered lepton and hadrons for different $x - Q^2$ regions over the detector polar angle / pseudorapidity coverage. Source: [3]

axis. The relationship between these two variables is given by the equation 1.1.

$$\eta = -\ln\left[\tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\right] \quad (1.1)$$

The definition of pseudorapidity allows one to categorize the detector regions

according to observable physics cases, the beam directions, and the available phase-space of final state particles, in particular, for an asymmetric configuration of beams' energies. In EIC, the beams' directions follow the configuration used at the HERA collider at DESY. the hadron beam travels in the positive z-direction/pseudorapidity and is said to be going "forward." The electron beam travels in the negative z-direction/pseudorapidity and is said to be going "backward" or in the "rear" direction. In figure 1.3, we see the illustration of the correlation between polar angle and the pseudorapidity in the $x - Q^2$ phase space for the EIC physics program.

Chapter Summary

The EIC will address some of the most fundamental questions in science regarding the visible universe. The physics goal of the EIC stands on five key pillars: **the mystery of nucleon spin, the origin of nucleon mass, 3D tomography of nucleons and nuclei, QCD at work in nuclei, and finally, the dense gluon system.** The success of the complex physics program, like that of the EIC, requires state-of-the art detector and accelerator facilities. The EIC will be the ultimate facility to shed light on the mystery of hadrons in an unprecedented phase space and with unparalleled accuracy. The first collisions are at our doorstep. Therefore, the successful construction of the central detector and the accelerator complex is among the highest priorities of the physics community involved in QCD and hadronic physics.

Chapter 2

Internal structure of the Nucleons: A brief introduction

A complete understanding of the internal structure of nucleons is one of the most demanding problems in contemporary nuclear and particle physics. There are multiple ways to access the information related to the internal structure of the nucleon; Deep Inelastic Scattering (DIS) of a lepton probe onto a nucleon target is a well established method to cleanly progress in exploring the nucleons. Historically, DIS is the approach relevant to obtaining the current level of our understanding of nucleon structure. In Inclusive DIS, the experimental measurements of the four momentum of the incoming and scattered lepton reveal information about the nucleon components, such as the number density or helicity distribution if the polarization states are considered. The process can be described by some well-known kinematic variables Q^2 , x_B , ν , y ; the definitions of these variables are given in the later part of the chapter. Nevertheless, the Inclusive DIS provides only a one dimensional picture of the nucleon, as it reveals the x_B distribution of (longitudinal) parton momenta in the direction of the nucleon momentum. However, due to confinement, the partons also have nonzero momenta in the (transverse) plane perpendicular to the nucleon momentum. Inside the transverse momentum dependent parton distributions (TMDs) the three dimensional parton structure of nucleons in momentum space is encoded. In the simplest interpretation of the parton model (known as the leading twist), there are single parton interactions, no multi parton correlations, and no soft re-scattering effects; for both quarks and gluons inside these spin $\frac{1}{2}$ nucleons, there exist a total of 8 TMDs. These functions reveal different insights into the dynamics of nucleons based on their correlations between the spins and the transverse momenta. In summary, TMDs describe the

distribution of partons in three dimensions in momentum space. This ultimate goal can be reached step by step by answering well-targeted questions such as:

1. How does it change with x_B ?
2. How wide is the distribution?
3. What is the effect of the spin?
4. Is there a difference between quark flavors?

TMDs can be accessed by different means; a) Semi Inclusive Deep Inelastic Scattering (SIDIS), b) Drell-Yann, c) hadro-production in e^+e^- collision, d) hadron-production in pp collision. This chapter will briefly introduce the basic elements of the formalism to address the key experimental observables via SIDIS. A brief discussion on Structure Functions, Parton Distribution Functions (PDF), factorization, and Fragmentation Functions (FFs) will be made. The formalism, in its entirety, will focus only on the key ideas of the experimental aspects and measured quantities in SIDIS.

2.1 QCD: An Introduction

A field theoretical approach to describe the theory of the strongly interacting quarks and gluons, the fundamental constituents of hadrons, is known as Quantum ChromoDynamics (QCD). According to QCD, in the high x_B regime, the partons are defined as the valence quarks. Similar to fluctuations of photons into electron-positron pairs in quantum electrodynamics, quark antiquark pairs can also be generated from the fluctuation of vector bosons of QCD, the gluons. These pair-produced charged partons are called sea quarks. Unlike photons, which are electrically charge neutral, gluons have color charges. This is due to the non-Abelian SU(3) structure of the theory. QCD is a re-normalizable quantum field theory. The quarks are spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ Dirac fields, Ψ_f^i with fractional charges, and are defined by quantum numbers composed of three colors and six flavors; the gluons are spin-1 vector fields, A_μ^a with eight color charges. The Lagrange density can be defined as:

$$L_{QCD}(\psi_f, A_\mu) = -\frac{1}{4}G^{\mu\nu,a}[A] + \sum_f \bar{\psi}_f(iD_\mu[A]\gamma^\mu - m_f)\psi_f$$

where, μ is the renormalization scale, $N_c =$ number of colors, $n_f =$ number of active flavors, $\beta_0 = \frac{11}{3}N_c - \frac{2}{3}n_f$, Λ_{QCD} the fundamental strong interaction scale and the coupling constant, at the first order:

$$\alpha_s(\mu) = \frac{1}{4\pi}g^2(\mu) \approx \frac{4\pi}{\beta_0 \ln(\frac{\mu^2}{\Lambda_{QCD}^2})} \quad (2.1)$$

Equation 2.1 shows that α_s decreases as μ increases, inferring that the strong force is weakly coupled when probed at sufficiently short distances. This phenomenon translates into large momentum transfers from an experimental perspective. This phenomenon is widely known as asymptotic freedom. Several experimental measurements have allowed us to obtain the dependence of the strong coupling constant on momentum transfer Q ; see figure 2.1. The QCD factorization allows us to

Figure 2.1: Evolution of the strong coupling constant with transferred momentum. The coupling constant decreases with increasing Q . Source:[4]

separate physics happening at different momentum scales. It is therefore possible to disentangle all process-independent non-perturbative contributions, such as Parton Distribution Functions (PDF), and perturbatively calculable short-distance partonic cross sections when computing high energy hadronic scattering cross sections. Process-dependent non-perturbative information can be neglected as power suppressed corrections. This leads to a dependence of the PDFs on the factorization scale (which determines the non perturbative contributions); this dependence is described by the Dokshitzer–Gribov–Lipatov–Altarelli–Parisi (DGLAP) evolution equations [5, 6, 7]. They are equations in QCD describing the variation of parton distribution functions with varying energy scales. Experimentally observed scaling violations in DIS (see figure 2.2) are important evidence for the correctness of

the equations and of QCD in general. Naturally, the cross sections must remain independent of the choice of the factorization scale. An essential aspect of TMDs

Figure 2.2: The QCD evolution of the structure function $F_2(x, Q^2)$. Such an evolution is predicted by the DGLAP equation. With increasing probe resolution one resolves the internal dynamics of quarks as prescribed by QCD. Source: [4]

concerns their scale-dependence (evolution) as predicted in QCD, which is considerably more involved than the evolution of the 1D PDFs. There is, therefore,

substantial interest in a quantitative understanding of the TMD evolution.

2.2 From Deep Inelastic Scattering (DIS) to Semi Inclusive DIS

In events where a lepton with four momentum (l) scatters off a nucleon with four momentum (P), we can inclusively measure the scattering angle of the lepton (θ_e) and the four momentum of the scattered lepton (l'). We assume the energy of the incoming (scattered) lepton is E (E'). This is an inclusive reaction. From the quantum field theoretical formalism, we understand that this is an electromagnetic interaction, and such an interaction can be mediated by the exchange of a virtual photon (γ^*). The photon can be considered to carry a four momentum q , which has the three momentum component \mathbf{q} and energy ν . A modified Feynman diagram in Fig. 2.3 (a) shows us the basics of the reaction, where the Z -axis has been chosen to be collinear with the direction of the nucleon and the virtual photon, known as the Gamma-Nucleon System (GNS). Notice that the remaining remnants of the reaction are undetected and are described as \mathbf{X} . In panel b of Fig. 2.3, we see a conceptual visualization of the reaction. The scheme assumes four momentum expressions in a light cone frame, where the parent nucleon is moving with a four momentum P^+ and the partons inside the nucleon are carrying a fractional (x_B) four momentum (k_i^+) of the total four momentum of the parent. The virtual photon collinear to P^+ makes a hard collision, and the partons inside are considered frozen in time during the collision due to the relativistic nature of the event. This is known as the infinite momentum frame. It is important at this point to define a few kinematic variables and clarify their physical meaning.

1. $Q^2 = -q^2 = 2EE'(1 + \cos\theta_e) = 4EE'\sin^2(\theta_e/2)$; defines the squared transferred four momentum to the virtual photon. Notice that a positive Q^2 implies a $q^2 < 0$; hence, the spacelike nature of the virtual photon. It is obvious that this quantity appears as the resolution of our probe.
2. The variable ν is the energy transferred to the virtual photon; hence, $\nu = E - E'$ (in the lab frame). This expression is the energy transferred to the virtual photon in the nucleons rest frame.
3. The fraction of the longitudinal momentum of the nucleon carried by the parton, $x_B = Q^2/(2P \cdot q)$, is another Lorentz invariant quantity. In literature, x_B is often interchanged with x .
4. Finally, the inelasticity of the process is defined as another Lorentz invariant quantity, $y = (P \cdot q)/(P \cdot l)$; in the lab frame, it is translated as $y = 1 - E'/E$.

5. Finally, the invariant mass of the final state hadronic system, W^2 , is defined as M_X^2 . A large value of W^2 implies a many particle final state and hence the regime of Deep Inelastic scattering.

Notice that both x_B and y are fractional quantities. Hence, they are bounded between 0 and 1. The available energy for the reaction is defined by the Mandelstem variable s , which is the square of the center of mass energy. One can show that Q^2 , x_B , and y are interrelated quantities, and their relationship is described by equations 2.2 for large s ;

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= \frac{Q^2}{2P \cdot q} \\
 x &= \frac{Q^2}{2M\nu} \text{ Invoking } \nu = \frac{P \cdot q}{M} \\
 xy &= \frac{Q^2}{s - M^2} \text{ Invoking } y = \frac{P \cdot q}{P \cdot l} \text{ and } 2 P \cdot l = s - M^2 \\
 Q^2 &= (s - M^2)xy \\
 Q^2 &= sxy; \text{ if } s \gg M^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Equation 2.2 also tells us the available kinematic coverage for a given centre of mass energy. The relationship between $Q^2 : x_B$ is linear for a given s and y . In figure 1.2 anticipated in Chapter 1 we see the phase-space covered by the Electron Ion Collider (EIC) as compared to the available data worldwide.

Figure 2.3: Panel (a): The Feynman Diagram of DIS process in Gamma Nucleon System. Panel (b): A qualitative picture demonstrating the collinear infinite momentum frame.

The cross-section for neutral-current DIS on unpolarized nucleons and nuclei, in the one photon exchange approximation (neglecting electroweak effects), can be written in terms of two structure functions F_2 and F_L

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dx.dQ^2} = \frac{4\pi\alpha^2}{x_B Q^4} \left(F_2(x, Q^2) \left(1 - y + \frac{y^2}{2}\right) - \frac{y^2}{2} F_L(x, Q^2) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

If the spin information is not summed over, then the cross-section (in equation 2.4) explicitly depends on the spin dependent structure functions, revealing information about the spin orientation of the quarks and gluons inside the proton (or nucleon in general). The cross-section can be written as :

$$\frac{d^2\Delta\sigma}{dx.dQ^2} = \frac{c}{Q^4} \left[\left(1 - \frac{y}{2} - \frac{4M^2xy^2}{Q^2}\right) g_1 - \frac{4M^2xy}{2} g_2 \right] \quad (2.4)$$

where c is a constant, $\Delta\sigma = \sigma_{\leftarrow}^{\rightarrow} - \sigma_{\rightarrow}^{\rightarrow}$, and the two spin dependent structure functions are g_1 and g_2 . The single arrow represents the polarization of the partons, and the reversal of the nuclear spin is indicated by the double arrow. In the Quark Parton Model (QPM), the assumption is that the parton and proton masses are negligible, and the electron scatters incoherently with the partons, and they do not self-interact. The structure functions $F_1(x, Q^2)$, $F_2(x, Q^2)$, and $g_1(x, Q^2)$ can be described in QPM, while $g_2(x, Q^2)$ cannot be described in the naive parton model, and its value is assumed to be zero. Experimentally, F_2 , F_L , and g_1 can be measured in inclusive scattering.

Already looking at Fig. 2.3, we understand that inclusive DIS physics provides crucial information about the internal structure of the nucleons, but only in the longitudinal realm. If we want information about the transverse world of the internal degrees of freedom of the nucleons, inclusive DIS is not enough. The kinematics of the scattered lepton do not carry any information related to the soft transverse motion of the parton.

The information related to the transverse dynamics of the partons is encoded in the transverse component of the fragmented hadron momentum (see Fig. (a) 2.4). In such case, the reaction modifies to:

$$e^-(l) + p(P) \rightarrow e^-(l') + h(P_h) + X$$

In Fig.2.4 (b), we notice that the non-zero transverse momentum of the partons is relevant. The question remains: how does the final state hadron encode this information. Let us concentrate on Fig. 2.5 (a), which zooms into the virtual photon nucleon interaction part of panel (a) of 2.4. We notice the virtual photon scatters with the parton with intrinsic transverse momentum k_T , and it fragments into a hadron with transverse momentum (wrt the virtual photon axis) P_{hT} . Another relevant variable is the angle ϕ_h of the hadron with respect to the lepton scattering plane.

In the qualitative picture, we have introduced a new variable z (interchangeably z_h) as the fractional momentum of the virtual photon carried by the outgoing hadron. The definition of z_h is given in equation 2.5.

Figure 2.4: Panel (a): The Feynman Diagram of SIDIS process in Gamma Nucleon System. Panel (b): Qualitative scheme to demonstrate the transverse momentum of partons are in the transverse plane of the Gamma Nucleon system.

$$z_h = \frac{P \cdot P_h}{P \cdot q} \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.5: Panel (a): The microscopic view of a SIDIS process demonstrates the interaction action between the virtual photon and the parton, it is evidential why the transverse momentum of the final state hadron act as a probe to the transverse momentum of the parton; (b): The angular dependency of the of the quark spin vector and the momentum components of the final state hadron.

From the momentum components, as depicted in Fig. 2.5 (a), we can write

down, for small P_{hT} :

$$\langle P_{hT}^2 \rangle = z_h^2 \langle k_T^2 \rangle + \langle P_\perp^2 \rangle \quad (2.6)$$

If the final state hadron is identified, we obtain information related to the flavor of the interacting quark. The identification of the final state hadron in coincidence with the scattered lepton is the realm of Semi Inclusive Deep Inelastic Scattering (SIDIS). The questions, therefore, boil down to (a) what is the cross-section of such a process, (b) how does QCD predict their evolution?

2.2.1 SIDIS in parton model

In the introduction of this chapter, we have mentioned PDFs and FFs. To state simply, the PDFs tell us the probability of finding a parton with certain kinematical characteristics inside a nucleon. In case we are interested in knowing the complete 3D picture, the PDFs are functions of x_B and k_T^2 . The FFs, on the other hand, tell us the probability that a parton with certain kinematical characteristics has fragmented into a final state hadron with z_h and other variables. A complete nucleon structure emerges when we determine these two building blocks from our experimental and theoretical knowledge.

In the leading twist, eight TMD PDFs are required to describe the internal degrees of freedom of the nucleon in a complete fashion. In Fig. 2.6 we summarize these PDFs according to the nucleon and quark polarization.

The diagonal terms can be interpreted in the following way:

- f_1 describes an unpolarized quark inside an unpolarized hadron.
- g_1 is the helicity distribution that describes a longitudinally polarized quark inside a longitudinally polarized hadron.
- h_1 is the transversity distribution that describes a transversely polarized quark inside a transversely polarized hadron

These are the collinear PDFs. The remaining terms describe situations where no collinear interpretations are available. For example, f_{1T}^\perp describes an unpolarized quark inside a transversely polarized hadron. This term is known as the Sivers function. Similar to the TMD PDFs, we can describe the TMD FFs, they are shown in Fig. 2.7 If we notice the transversely polarized quark in an unpolarized nucleon, from Fig. 2.6 and 2.7 we understand that the Collins Fragmentation Function and Boer-Mulders function couple to describe the process in which a transversely polarized quark from an unpolarized nucleon fragments into a final state hadron. Note that, similar to the leading quarks, two analogous matrices exist for the gluons as well. They are not discussed in this chapter.

Leading Quark TMDPDFs Quark Spin

		Quark Polarization		
		Un-Polarized (U)	Longitudinally Polarized (L)	Transversely Polarized (T)
Nucleon Polarization	U	$f_1 = \text{○} \cdot$ Unpolarized		$h_1^\perp = \text{○} \uparrow - \text{○} \downarrow$ Boer-Mulders
	L		$g_1 = \text{○} \rightarrow - \text{○} \leftarrow$ Helicity	$h_{1L}^\perp = \text{○} \rightarrow \uparrow - \text{○} \rightarrow \downarrow$ Worm-gear
	T	$f_{1T}^\perp = \text{○} \uparrow - \text{○} \downarrow$ Sivers	$g_{1T}^\perp = \text{○} \rightarrow \uparrow - \text{○} \rightarrow \downarrow$ Worm-gear	$h_1 = \text{○} \uparrow - \text{○} \downarrow$ Transversity $h_{1T}^\perp = \text{○} \rightarrow \uparrow - \text{○} \rightarrow \downarrow$ Pretzelosity

Figure 2.6: TMD PDFs of the leading Quarks at leading twist.

Under the single photon exchange approximation, and considering the unpolarized case, we can write down the cross-section of a SIDIS process. In such a process, the proton is unpolarized, and the cross section is integrated over all possible transverse momentum of the parton. The expression of the process can be seen in equation 2.7.

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dx dy dz_h} = \sum_{i,j} \int_x^1 d\xi \int_{z_h}^1 d\zeta f_{i/p}(\xi) D_{h/j}(\zeta) \frac{d\hat{\sigma}_{i,j}}{dx dy dz_h} \left[1 + O\left(\frac{\Lambda_{QCD}^2}{Q^2}\right) \right] \quad (2.7)$$

The sum over indices (i,j) ensures the sum over every possible flavor quantum number at the interaction vertex for both the interacting parton and the outgoing parton that hadronizes. It depends on three main ingredients:

- $f_{i/p}(\xi)$ is the probability of finding a parton i inside the proton p with a momentum fraction ξ . This is the collinear unpolarized PDF of the parton i inside the proton.
- $D_{h/j}(\zeta)$ is the probability of a parton j fragmenting into a hadron h with a fractional momentum ζ of the parton.
- $d\hat{\sigma}_{i,j}/dx dy dz_h$, the differential cross section of $e^-(l) + i(k) \rightarrow e^-(l') + j(p) + X$

Figure 2.7: TMD FFs of the leading quarks at leading twist.

The transverse momentum P_{hT} of the final state hadron in a SIDIS process is an essential quantity to measure. We have seen from Fig. 2.5 that the intrinsic transverse momentum k_T is encoded inside P_{hT} via the expression in equation 2.6. Notice that for a large transverse momentum, $P_{hT} \sim Q$, any information about the k_T of the interacting parton is lost. As for large transverse momentum ($P_{hT} \sim Q^2$) the fragmenting quark is most likely to be produced from QCD radiative effects such as $q \rightarrow q + g$.

Therefore, we can generalize equation 2.7 involving (P_{hT} for $\Lambda_{QCD} \lesssim P_{hT} \ll Q$) in equation 2.8.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\sigma}{dx dy dz_h d^2\mathbf{P}_{hT}} = & \\ \sum_i \hat{\sigma}_{ii}(Q, x, y) \int d^2\mathbf{P}_\perp d^2\mathbf{k}_T \delta^{(2)}(\mathbf{P}_{hT} - z_h \mathbf{k}_T - \mathbf{P}_\perp) f_{i/p}(x, \mathbf{k}_T) D_{h/i}(z_h, \mathbf{P}_\perp) & \quad (2.8) \\ \cdot \left[1 + O\left(\frac{P_{hT}^2}{Q^2}, \frac{\Lambda_{QCD}^2}{Q^2}\right) \right] & \end{aligned}$$

We have now set $\xi = x$, $\zeta = z_h$; and integrating out all possible values of the intrinsic transverse momentum \mathbf{k}_T and the hadron momentum orthogonal to the

original parton trajectory (i.e., the acquired transverse momentum) \mathbf{P}_\perp , which sums to the measured hadron's transverse momentum. The $\hat{\sigma}_i^{TMD}(Q, x, y)$ can be calculated perturbatively using the rules of quantum electrodynamics.

The introduction of this minimal theoretical framework allows us to appreciate that one can extend the framework for the Polarized SIDIS case as well. At this moment, we ask ourselves, what can we measure in an experiment? In the experiment, we access the so-called structure functions that encode the TMD PDF and the TMD FF. In equation 2.9, we see the complete cross-section of a Polarized SIDIS process, where the beam (lepton), target (nucleon), and the virtual photon polarization have been considered to construct the structure functions. In addition, the cross-section contains angular modulations of the final state hadrons in the lepton-nucleon frame. A discussion on the complete and formal origin of these terms is beyond the scope of this thesis. However, the amplitudes of these modulations give information on all possible spin-spin and spin-orbit correlations between the quark and the nucleon, i.e. it provides full access to the 8 TMD PDFs in figure 2.7.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d^6\sigma}{dx dy dz_h d\phi_S d\phi_h dP_{hT}^2} &= \frac{\alpha_{em}^2}{xyQ^2} \left(1 - y + \frac{1}{2}y^2 \right) \\
 &\left[F_{Uu,T} + \cos(2\phi_h) p_1 F_{UU}^{\cos(2\phi_h)} + S_L \sin(2\phi_h) p_1 F_{UL}^{\sin(2\phi_h)} \right. \\
 &+ S_L \lambda p_2 F_{LL} + S_T \sin(\phi_h - \phi_S) F_{UT,T}^{\sin(\phi_h - \phi_S)} \\
 &+ S_T \sin(\phi_h + \phi_S) p_1 F_{UT}^{\sin(\phi_h + \phi_S)} + \lambda S_T \cos(\phi_h - \phi_S) p_2 F_{LT}^{\cos(\phi_h - \phi_S)} \\
 &\left. + S_T \sin(3\phi_h - \phi_S) p_1 F_{UT}^{\sin(3\phi_h - \phi_S)} \right] + \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

where $p_1 = \frac{1-y}{1-y+\frac{1}{2}y^2}$, $p_2 = \frac{y(1-\frac{1}{2}y)}{1-y+\frac{1}{2}y^2}$, $p_3 = \frac{(2-y)\sqrt{1-y}}{1-y+\frac{1}{2}y^2}$, $p_4 = \frac{y\sqrt{1-y}}{1-y+\frac{1}{2}y^2}$.

The $F_{XY[Z]}^{[f(\varphi_h)]}$ are the so-called structure functions. The indices X, Y, Z represent the polarization state of the beam, target, and the virtual photons. The angular terms in superscript describe a modulation with respect to φ_h and φ_S as described in Fig. 2.5. At high Q^2 , they can be described in terms of TMD PDFs and TMD FFs. Detection of the angular modulation is the key experimental methodology that one needs to perform. The number of detected hadrons with specific modulation, under given beam and target polarization.

2.2.2 SIDIS in quark parton model : Factorization

The intuitive partonic pictures need to be justified or derived in real QCD. This is the final goal. There is a critical challenge; it is ambiguous in relativistic quantum field theories like QCD to differentiate between what is genuinely intrinsic to bound-state particles (the hadrons) and effects that are specific to the interactions.

In QCD, as we already discussed in the brief introduction, the notion of the parton as a nearly freely propagating point-like quantum of the quark or gluon field is most meaningful in contexts where asymptotic freedom applies. Therefore, a strong theoretical interpretation of the partonic picture can be achieved if one can isolate the short distance part (hard interaction) of an interaction and calculate it with small-coupling techniques, independently of nonperturbative details of physics at large distance scales. Complications can arise when there is an interplay between short distance scale and large distance scale processes. The aim of QCD factorization is to be able to separate (factorize) these different categories to calculate and interpret them; and then to reassemble them to describe physical observables.

At this point, we ask ourselves: how can we schematically imagine the factorization in SIDIS? The cross-section of the SIDIS can be realized as a convolution of three independent processes. 1. The soft part: the $q(x)$ s are the PDFs. 2. The hard process: σ_q is the cross-section of the absorption of the virtual photon by the quark q , and 3. the soft part: the $D_q^h(z)$ s are the FFs. In this factorization ansatz, processes 1. and 3. are non perturbative, and 2. is a perturbative term.

The PDFs and the FFs do not change by altering processes. In this sense, they are Universal. For example, the extraction of FFs can also be done from e^+e^- and hadron-hadron collisions. This is known as the Universality of the Fragmentation Functions. Kniehl, Kramer, and Pötter tested experimentally that the FFs are universal [8]. Different models have been developed to describe how quarks confine together to make a hadron. The fragmentation functions extracted from e^+e^- data showed their dependence on Q^2 . In figure 2.8 the dependence on Q^2 of the Fragmentation Functions extracted from e^+e^- data is shown.

The theoretical description of the e^+e^- annihilation has been obtained with high accuracy, and it is, so far, the cleanest process without invoking model-dependent algorithms for quark-flavor tagging, only a limited flavor separation is possible. It is important to note that SIDIS allows us to access the FFs separately for the quarks and antiquarks, along with the parton kinematics.

The evolution of FFs is similar to the evolution of PDFs. The Q^2 evolution of the collinear FFs can also be described by the DGLAP evolution equation. For each hadron species h , one FF can describe its relation to one quark flavor q . Considering only light quarks, we therefore have 12 FFs for positive and negative hadrons. Aiding the QCD improved parton model, isospin symmetry, or charge conjugation reduces the number of independent FFs. Based on the fact that quarks are either valence or sea, the FFs can be grouped as favoured or unfavoured, respectively. Therefore, it becomes necessary to identify hadrons in an experiment to understand the flavor of the participating quark in the reaction.

Figure 2.8: The e^+e^- fragmentation function for all particles versus x for different \sqrt{s} which has same meaning of Q^2 is shown in the left, in the right the fragmentation function versus \sqrt{s} for different x [4].

2.2.3 Accessing the Fragmentation Function: Via SIDIS

The FFs can be accessed by means of hadron multiplicities. Hadron multiplicities are the number of hadrons produced per DIS events. At Leading Order, the multiplicities are not complex convolutions of the PDFs and FFs, but simple products weighted by the square of the quark electric charge.

$$M^h(x, Q^2, z_h) = \frac{d\sigma^{lN \rightarrow l'hX}}{d\sigma^{lN \rightarrow l'X}} = \frac{d\sigma^h/dxdQ^2}{d\sigma^{DIS}dxdQ^2} \quad (2.10)$$

$$M^h(x, Q^2, z_h) = \frac{\sum_q e_q^2 q(x, Q^2) D_q^h(z_h, Q^2)}{\sum_q e_q^2 q(x, Q^2)}$$

By measuring the $M^h(x, Q^2, z_h)$ for identified hadrons charged positively or negatively, one can distinguish between D_q^h and $D_{\bar{q}}^h$ [9] respectively.

The precision measurements, alongside theoretical advancements, allow us to validate the Standard Model of fundamental interactions and our picture of matter under extreme conditions. This gives the improvement of our knowledge of PDFs

and FFs a crucial role in the search for new physical phenomena. The requirement for increased precision becomes especially relevant in the case of quarks generated through QCD radiation (sea quarks), which are typically less constrained than their valence counterparts. The s-quark being the lightest sea quark inside a proton. In an experiment where pions are copiously produced, efficient separation of pions from kaons allows for a stringent constraint on the s-quark dynamics. Therefore, the final state hadron identification is central to the SIDIS program, which enables us to access the non-perturbative information of QCD.

The Electron Ion Collider (EIC) will play a central role in this physics program by accessing physics in an unprecedented phase-space [10]. The constraints on global extraction coming from the EIC would allow us to study the internal parton dynamics and QCD in general with unparalleled precision and accuracy.

2.3 Summary

In order to understand the internal structure of the nucleus from a naive 1D picture, we cannot rely on the scattered lepton information alone. A complete 3D picture emerges when we access the transverse dynamics of the partons. In non-perturbative QCD the parton distribution function (PDF) and the fragmentation function (FF) are two key ingredients for experimentally accessing the internal dynamics of the partons through the observed final state hadrons. The measurements of identified hadron multiplicities allow us to access the FF and essentially the dynamics of quarks of different flavors. Therefore, the efficient identification of final state hadrons plays a central role in this physics channel. The EIC physics scope will greatly explore such a physics program, enabling us to decode the details about the internal structure of hadrons and the mechanisms leading to confinement.

Chapter 3

The ePIC experiment at the EIC Collider

The ePIC [11] detector is an important part of the EIC project; therefore, it must be able to cope with the whole EIC physics scope (Chapter 1). To this end, it has to (i) detect and identify the scattered electrons, (ii) detect the scattered hadrons, (iii) measure the kinematical parameters of the reaction products, and (iv) discriminate among the different hadron species.

The convention to define the direction of the detector has been discussed in chapter 1, and can be seen schematically in figure 1.3.

The detector design foresees a central detector sitting in the interaction region. It is approximately 9.5 m long. In the central detector, the momentum analysis is provided by a superconducting solenoid of magnetic field of 1.7 T and a tracking system available in different layers; starting from the most internal ones and moving outward. The central detector is also equipped with devices for particle identification, and electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters.

The central detector will cover a pseudorapidity (η , defined in equation 1.1) range of $-3.5 \div 3.5$. To achieve the highest possible degree of hermeticity, within technical limits, far detectors are foreseen along the outgoing beamline. In the far-forward region, tracking systems detect particles scattered at very small angles, together with electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters capable of measuring neutral particles required for exclusive measurements. The backward region is dedicated to luminosity measurement and monitoring and hosts a set of tracking detectors and electromagnetic calorimeters to tag low Q^2 events. An overall schematic image of the ePIC detector is presented in Fig. 3.1. The choice of the technologies based on the requirements for the EIC physics scope.

The **tracking system** includes detectors based on monolithic silicon trackers and MicroPattern Gaseous Detector (MPGD) technologies. Dedicated simulation

Figure 3.1: The ePIC detector. Top: the whole detector is shown including the far detectors situated along the outgoing beam lines. Bottom left: a zoom of the central detector. Bottom right: the most relevant parameters of the ePIC detector are summarized.

exercises confirm that the tracking performance, and therefore the momentum and vertex resolution, strongly depends on the material budget. The sensors selected for the silicon tracking are thin, low material and low power consumption MAPS in 65 nm technology, currently under development for the upgrade of the LHC experiment ALICE [12]. The thin sensors can also be arranged in a virtually support-less curved arrangement, together their very low power consumption, possibility of large sensor size, allow one to design the innermost layers, namely the vertex arrangement, with an extremely low material budget of only 0.05% of a radiation length per layer for the three vertex layers. The same sensors, arranged in a supported configuration, are considered for the surrounding layers and the endcaps. The adopted MAPSs offer very fine spatial resolution, of order $O(15\mu\text{m})$, but provide limited time information, which should be provided by the complementary tracking devices. The tracking system is completed by large-area MPGDs based on cylindrical MICROMEAS and the novel $\mu\text{R-WELL}$ technologies, which can achieve a time resolution of order $O(20\text{ ns})$.

Electromagnetic calorimetry is implemented using different technologies in the various regions of the central detector. The high resolution required for measuring the backward scattered electrons is provided by a fine-granularity PbWO_4 crystal calorimeter.

The barrel region is instrumented with a hybrid electromagnetic calorimeter that

combines light-collecting and imaging techniques. Its design employs scintillating-fiber (SciFi) calorimetry, with fibers embedded in lead, together with imaging calorimetry based on monolithic silicon sensors (AstroPix). Shower imaging is achieved through four layers of silicon imaging sensors interleaved with SciFi/Pb layers, followed by a thick SciFi/Pb section, resulting in a total thickness of approximately 20 radiation lengths.

This design enables the detection of scattered and secondary electrons and their separation from pions, the reconstruction of the full kinematic information of photons, and sufficient spatial resolution to identify, up to high momenta, photons originating from neutral pion decays. In the forward endcap, electromagnetic calorimetry is realized with a matrix of tungsten powder and epoxy incorporating embedded scintillating fibers.

Hadron calorimetry is based on ion absorbers and scintillating counters as active elements. The forward and backward calorimeters makes use of a novel approach with the sensors, which are Silicon PhotoMultipliers (SiPM) embedded in the scintillating tiles, while the signals are conveyed to the rear calorimeter face where they are collected.

Particle identification is discussed in Chapter 4.

The accelerator and detector effort are complemented by **polarimetry** requirements. Rapid, precise beam polarization measurements will be crucial for meeting the goals of the EIC physics program as the uncertainty in the polarization propagates directly into the uncertainty for relevant observables as asymmetries. The basic requirements for beam polarimetry are non-destructive with minimal impact on the beam lifetime, uncertainty at the 1% level, the capacity of measuring the beam polarization for each bunch in the ring with rapid, quasi-online analysis in order to provide timely feedback for accelerator setting up. The electron beam polarimetry will be based on the well established Compton polarimeter techniques, where the polarized electrons scatter from 100% circularly polarized laser photons. This approach offers the advantage that both longitudinal and transversal polarizations are measured. Hadron polarimetry has been successfully performed for the RHIC polarized proton beams for nearly two decades. Through continual development a relative systematic uncertainty $<1.5\%$ was achieved for the most recent RHIC polarized proton run. This, as the only hadron polarimeter system at a high energy collider it is the natural starting point for hadron polarimetry at the EIC. Hadron polarization will be measured via a transverse single spin left right asymmetry in the pp interaction on targets by plastic material (H-C composition), where the experimental challenge is the control of the background events.

Chapter 4

The ePIC dual radiator RICH

4.1 Particle identification

In experimental particle and nuclear physics Particle IDentification (PID) plays a crucial role. Particles can be identified by several means. One of the techniques used at high energy is to estimate the invariant mass (m) of the particle. The relativistic formulation of momentum (p) is given in equation 4.1

$$\begin{aligned} p &= m\gamma\beta c \\ m &= \frac{p}{\gamma\beta c} \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

where γ , β and c carry the usual meaning of special relativity. Therefore, the mass can be determined if the momentum and the velocity of the particle are measured independently. A magnetic spectrometer, for instance, can provide a measurement of the momentum while dedicated detectors are requested for the measurement of the velocity.

The uncertainty associated in the measurement of the mass can be obtained by propagating the uncertainties in equation 4.1:

$$\left(\frac{\delta m}{m}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\delta p}{p}\right)^2 + \left(\gamma^2 \frac{\delta\beta}{\beta}\right)^2 \tag{4.2}$$

From equation 4.2 it is evident that the accurate measurement of the velocity becomes critical in the invariant mass determination for high momentum particles. In fact, the term dependent on the velocity uncertainty is enhanced by the factor γ^4 .

Figure 4.1: The histogram shows the relative yield of charged hadrons in the ePIC experiment from Pythia simulations for 18×275 GeV ep collisions as a function of momenta and pseudorapidity, η . The contours indicate the 3σ separation region of the different ePIC PID subsystems for π/κ (a), κ/p (b), and e/π (c), respectively.

Four different technologies are used in the ePIC experiment to measure the particle velocity. They are based either on the measurement of the Time-of-Flight (ToF) or on Cherenkov imaging techniques. Each technology is effective in a well-defined momentum range. Therefore, the wide space-phase domain to be covered in the ePIC experiment impose the adoption of multiple technologies (Fig. 4.1).

Ring Imaging Cherenkov detectors (Sec. 4.2.1) are extremely powerful devices to provide β with fine resolution for high energy charged particles. Moreover, they can provide the measurement over a wide phase-space range. Therefore, they are powerful detectors for particle identification [13].

4.2 The Cherenkov effect

A charged particle moving in a dielectric matter polarizes the atoms and the molecules around it. If the speed of charged particle is slower compared to the speed of light in that medium, then the polarized atoms or molecules get enough time to relax before the charge is displaced. However, interesting physics appears when the charge particle is ultra-relativistic. The deformation caused by the local electric field of the charged particle is not restored before the charge moves to a new point in spacetime. This manifests into a far-field electromagnetic radiation. The radiation is emitted with speed $c' = \frac{c}{n(\lambda)}$ where c is the speed of light in vacuum and $n(\lambda)$ is the refractive index of the material at the wavelength λ of the wave.

The Cherenkov effect manifests this physics. In a dielectric material a trough-going particle with speed v greater than the light speed in the material $v > c'$ generates the Cherenkov radiation [14]. The radiation is caused by breaking the symmetry of the light emission, resulting in a constructing interference and in a measurable macroscopic effect. Respect to the particle trajectory, this emission is uniform in the azimuthal angle, with a polar angle θ_c that depends on the velocity of the particle. From a simple geometric calculation the Cherenkov equation results:

$$\cos(\theta_c) = \frac{1}{\beta n(\lambda)} \quad (4.3)$$

Hence the measurement of the polar angle, known as Cherenkov angle, allows one to determine the velocity of the ultra-relativistic charged particle. Hence, by measuring the momentum of a particle and the Cherenkov angle, it is possible to determine its mass. The idea to identify mass of charged particles by exploiting the directional properties of the Cherenkov radiation was conceived by Roberts [15].

Two important consequences of the Cherenkov equation have to be underlined.

- There exists a β threshold $\beta_{th} = \frac{1}{n}$, namely the Cherenkov radiation is emitted only if the charged particle moving through the medium has a $\beta > \beta_{th}$. The threshold momentum depends on the refractive index of the material and on

the mass of the particle. This threshold set a lower limit for direct particle identification by Cherenkov techniques.

- For $\beta \rightarrow 1$, the emission reaches a saturation angle defined as $\cos(\theta_{max}) = \frac{1}{n}$, which is the same for every particle and depends only on the refractive index. This means that different particle with high momentum emits radiation at the same angle, resulting in an upper limit in the momentum range for the particle identification.

The number of Cherenkov photons emitted at a specific wavelength is determined by the Frank and Tamm Law. For a given radiator, the number of emitted photon is proportional to $\sin^2(\theta_c)$.

4.2.1 Ring Image Cherenkov detectors

Ring Imaging Cherenkov detectors (RICH) are extremely powerful devices to provide β with fine resolution for high energy charged particles. Moreover, they can provide the measurement over a wide phase-space range. Therefore, they are powerful detectors for particle identification [13].

RICHes are based on the following principle: thanks to a photon sensor with high spatial resolution the ring image generated by the passage of a particle in an appropriate radiator can be analyzed extracting the Cherenkov angle. A RICH detector can either be used in a focusing or in a proximity-focusing mode. For **high momentum particle identification**, a lower value of refractive index is chosen, to allow saturation of the Cherenkov angle at larger momenta. Therefore gaseous radiator are adopted. The low refractive index results in a small number of produced photons per unit length, much smaller than for a solid state radiator. To recover a larger number of photons a long radiator is used. Therefore, the photon emission point is affected by a large uncertainty. This is cured with an optical system. Thanks to the property of a focusing mirror, the emitted Cherenkov photons with parallel trajectories, namely the photons emitted with the same azimuthal angle at different points along the particle trajectory, are focused onto a same point on the photodetector surface. Considering photons emitted with different azimuth, the resulting image is a ring (Fig. 4.2 (a)). A focusing RICH detector is composed by three essential components:

1. A radiator, where the Cherenkov radiation is produced;
2. A photodetector system, to collect and detect the photons emitted;
3. A set of mirrors to focus the emitted Cherenkov photons onto the sensor surface.

When the refractive index is higher, namely when **low momentum particles** have to be identified, the radiator can be thin and no focusing optics is needed. This is a proximity focusing RICH and a sensor plane is placed downstream of the radiator at an appropriate proximity gap to guarantee the formation of a ring-like image (Fig. 4.2 (b)).

A different approach to Cherenkov imaging devices is by the Detection of Internally Reflected Cherenkov light (DIRC). In DIRCs, quartz bars are at the same time radiators and light guides; in fact, the Cherenkov light is trapped inside the bars by total internal reflection and it travels by a zig-zag path preserving the angular information until it reaches a photodetector (Fig. 4.2 (c)). The radiator

Figure 4.2: Schematics of Cherenkov imaging counters: (a) focusing RICH, (b) proximity focusing RICH and (c) DIRC.

selection is the first step in the design of a detector, taking into account relevant parameters. The radiator must have a refractive index adequate for PID in the desired momentum range. It's also important to choose a radiator transparent in the wavelength range of the emitted photons that the selected photosensor can detect, typically the visible range or the ultraviolet region. There will be however an intrinsic uncertainty in the measurement due to the chromatic dispersion of the radiator medium. This results in an irreducible limit in the resolution of the reconstructed Cherenkov angle of the single photo-electron.

4.3 Particle identification at the ePIC experiment

The PID system of the ePIC central detector has a double mission:

- The identification of the scattered electron in the final state is crucial for

the whole physics scope. It is largely based on combining tracking and electromagnetic calorimetry information. Nevertheless, also due to the high production rate of pions in a wide phase-space range of the final state, the purity of the electron sample is not as good as desired, in particular at low momenta, below a few GeV/c. The PID system can largely contribute to refine the electron-pion separation at low momenta.

- The identification of the different hadron species (π , κ , p) as required by the physics scope, in particular for the measurements of SIDIS (Chapter 2).

The physics requirements of EIC has driven the choice of technologies for PID (Fig. 4.1). The wide range of particle momenta impose the choice of a variety of technologies equipping the overall acceptance of the ePIC central detector, namely the electron going direction (backward region), the barrel region and the hadron going direction (forward direction) resulting in the arrangement shown in Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Crosscut view of the ePIC central detector. The PID devices are indicated in color.

The **backward region** is equipped with a proximity focusing RICH (pFRICH) detector and ToF provided by the photosensors of the pFRICH itself, which are sitting in the detector acceptance. The pFRICH uses an aerogel radiator of refractive index 1.045. A large proximity gap is used to improve the single photo-electron Cherenkov angle resolution. High Rate Pico-second Photon Detectors (HRPPD) produced by INCOM¹ have been chosen as photosensors. The pFRICH is designed

¹Incom Inc., 294 Southbridge Rd, Charlton, Massachusetts, 01507, United States

to deliver π/κ separation up to 9 GeV/c. Thanks to fast timing response, the Cherenkov photons generated by the through going particles in the fused silica (quartz) window of the HRPPDs can be used to provide a timing reference in the backward region.

The PID in the **barrel region** will be delivered by a high performance DIRC (hpDIRC) and ToF based on capacitively coupling Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (AC-LGAD) sensors. LGADs are silicon sensors providing very fine space and time resolution. The modified version AC-LGAD also provides $\sim 100\%$ filling factor. Strip sensor channels (500 μm x 1 mm) equip the barrel. In the barrel region thanks to the ToF device π and κ can be separated at 3σ level up to 2 GeV and electron and pion can be separated up to 500 MeV.

A DIRC counter has been selected for high momentum PID in the barrel region because of its compact radial size of only 7-8 cm. It is anticipated to achieve a π/κ separation with a minimum significance of 3 standard deviations for momenta up to 6 GeV/c. This performance represents an improvement of nearly twice the current state-of-the-art DIRC systems, primarily thanks to the introduction of a 3-layer focusing lenses, small pixel sensors, and fine time resolution readout electronics. The photosensors for hpDIRC are the same used for the pFRICH.

Particle identification in the **forward region** is performed by a ToF system and a dual radiator RICH (dRICH). The dRICH is discussed in the dedicated Sec. 4.4.

ToF is provided by AC-LGAD sensors, similarly to what adopted in the barrel region. A (500 μm x 500 μm) pixel channel configuration is selected to cope with the high occupancy expected in the forward region. In the forward region 3σ π - κ and electron- π separation can be achieved up to 2.7 GeV and 800 MeV respectively.

4.4 dRICH

The dRICH (Fig. 4.4) employs two different radiators, namely aerogel and gas, to cover a wide momentum range with a substantial overlap of the two regions served by them. The dRICH has been designed with aerogel, 4 cm thick with refractive index 1.026 at $\lambda = 400$ nm. The chromatic dispersion has been measured to be $dn/d\lambda = 6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ at 400 nm wavelength. The gas radiator is by 1.2 m of C_2F_6 with refractive index $n = 1.00086$ at STP and excellent chromatic dispersion $dn/d\lambda = 0.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ at wavelength $\lambda = 350$ nm [16]. The two radiators provide PID for the lower and higher momentum regions, respectively.

The RICH design (Fig. 4.4) is based on the replica of six identical arrangements of mirrors and spherical photosensor sectors. Each mirror focuses the reflected photons onto the corresponding photosensor area. The dRICH covers the pseudorapidity range $1.5 \div 3.5$.

SiPMs are used as detector of single photons. These silicon sensor are matrices

of micro pixels ($50\text{-}75\ \mu\text{m}$), which operate in Geiger mode. The choice of these sensors is a challenge because SiPMs are affected by relevant dark counting rate and, because of the Geiger operation mode, the dark discharges are identical to the signals generated by the conversion of a single photons. The dark count rate is mitigated operating the SiPMs at low temperature ($O(-40^\circ\text{C})$). The dark counts increase due to radiation damage. The SiPMs have been qualified as adequate sensors for the use in the dRICH via a robust R&D program [17], shortly recalled in the following. The increase of dark counting rate has been measured for given fluences. The recovery obtained with thermal cycles at high temperature has been determined and confirmed in repeated cycles alternating irradiation and annealing. The possibility to perform the SiPM annealing in situ by heating with the application of reversed voltage bias has also been proven. It has been established that, at ePIC, the SiPMs used in the dRICH will never overcome the rate of 300 kHz per SiPM unit. The impact of such a dark count rate is one of the topics studied in this thesis.

An extruded sensor box hosts the spherical sensor planes with 10 cm attached services (including front-end electronics, cooling and back-end services). This systems provide the entire acceptance of the dRICH. Each Photon Detection Unit (PDU) is grouped into 2×2 matrix of photosensitive surfaces with a 0.2 mm gap. Each sensor surface contains 8×8 SiPMs of $3 \times 3\ \text{mm}^2$ surface. Therefore, a total of 256 SiPMs are present in a PDU.

Figure 4.4: (Left) Two views of the dRICH detector model; the major components are highlighted. (Center) dRICH detector box model with 208 photodetector units forming a curved active surface. (Right) Model of the dRICH photodetector unit with its major components highlighted.

The dRICH design has been supported by robust simulation exercises. The simulation campaigns performed so far resulted in the current baseline parameters. The outcome of the simulation studies is in agreement with testbeam exercises performed with dRICH prototypes. Nevertheless, the optimization of the details

is still ongoing together with the deeper and deeper assessment of the detector response and performance. It is already established that the baseline configuration provides a comfortable momentum overlap of the domains of the two radiators and a 3σ π/κ separation up to ~ 50 GeV/ c in the most demanding high pseudo-rapidity region. Further studies are presented in this thesis in the following Chapters and they are the original contribution of the student.

Chapter 5

The ePIC software scheme

5.1 Introduction

The ePIC experiment has a complex software framework. A detailed overview of the software stack goes beyond the scope of this thesis. However, as this thesis discusses results that have been obtained using the software framework, we briefly discuss the framework and the relevant parts that have been largely used or modified for the studies included in this thesis.

A simulation framework can be described in an overly simplified form, as shown in Fig.5.1. In order to characterize the performance of a detector, it is necessary to ensure realistic modeling of the detector and to generate simulated hits using all possible physics involvement. In general, the simulation framework takes care of describing the physics processes; the user includes the relevant processes and provides a realistic detector description. The simplified scheme in Fig. 5.1 will become more complex as our description proceeds, but we will preserve the color code for clear understanding. This chapter is therefore going to discuss the modeling of the dRICH detector in the ePIC software framework, the simulation, reconstruction of the simulated data, and finally the validation of performance. This chapter does not discuss the results; it focuses on the skeleton of the relevant software developed within the framework or at the user level.

Figure 5.1: A simple scheme to demonstrate the detector validation in a simulation framework.

5.2 Detector Description

In a large collaboration, like in ePIC, the description of the detector is complicated. The complication further increases when the demand is to model the detector based on a single source of information, which should serve multiple purposes. The incorporation of a consistent detector description into the simulation, reconstruction, and analysis stages is a cornerstone of complicated detector design. At this point, it is necessary to define the "detector description". By detector description, we have to include many elements: the geometry, material, detection efficiency, the relevant parameters to perform alignment and calibration, the description of readout surfaces, the active area, and many other important details. The ePIC collaboration has invested a significant effort to identify one of the most cutting edge software packages to serve this important job.

The ePIC detector systems are described using the software package known as DD4hep [18]. It describes the detector in every aspect mentioned above and addresses them at all stages; namely, simulation, reconstruction, and analysis. The main components of this package are the **ROOT** [19] geometry package, which is used for the construction and visualization of the geometry, and the Geant4 simulation toolkit [20], which can be interfaced via DD4hep to perform simulation studies.

At the user level, this software has two important aspects: a) the description of the detector parameters via a .xml file, and b) the construction of the detector by reading the parameters in C++. In Fig. 5.2, we demonstrate an example of our detector description. In the left panel, we see a snapshot of the parametrization to construct the sensor sphere of the dRICH; whereas in the right panel, we see the labeled diagram of the dRICH detector. As an example, if the user is interested in studying the effect of different aerogel parameters, subsequent modifications will be made to the aerogel parameters described in the .xml file; on the other hand, if the user is interested in making different arrangements of the SiPM matrices, the subsequent part in the C++ method dedicated to dRICH geometry has to be modified.

It is now time to make our first advancement into our initial scheme (5.1). In Fig. 5.3, we see that our detector description block essentially has two parts invoking the ROOT geometry handler. In this part, we are providing the parameters and developing methods to construct the detector element. The most important point is that the description is universal; that is to say, at any point in the software chain, for any detector subsystem, its description can be accessed in a unique fashion.

Figure 5.2: An example of DD4hep at work. Left: snapshot of detector parameters, right: visualization of detector elements.

Figure 5.3: The detector description is not monolithic. The ROOT geometry handler segregates the development part from parameters.

5.3 Simulation

In section 5.2, we mentioned that DD4hep has two jobs to execute: a) to describe the geometry and b) to interface Geant4 for detector simulation. In this section, we discuss the interfacing between the described detector and Geant4. In ePIC, this task is performed by the npsim plugin, which preserves the optical parameters of the Cherenkov photons, an essential information for dRICH studies. Therefore, in the following chapters, whenever we mention simulation, we mean DD4hep geometry has been interfaced with Geant4 by the npsim plugin.

More precisely, the simulation response in the active elements of the detector is not implemented by the toolkit; in fact, the very specific technical choices strictly dictate the simulation output. In Geant4 this response is computed in software constructs called Sensitive Detectors. To simulate the detector hits in DD4hep methods, one needs to define the sensitive volume. In the case of dRICH, the sensitive surface is not described in terms of single SiPMs. It is formed by Photon Detection Units (PDU), each one being formed by an arrangement of SiPMs as described in section 4.4). The simulated hits can be assigned to the hit SiPM at the analysis or reconstruction level by accessing the DD4hep geometry. This procedure also takes into account the dead-area separating the individual SiPMs.

The events that are to be simulated can be directly fed to npsim. These events can consist of single particles with a given four momentum or events generated from Physics simulators like Pythia. For a more involved simulation in momentum and angular acceptance bins, the events are generated and passed as a HepMC file.

The output of the simulated data is a ROOT file, which respects the data-model adopted by the ePIC experiment, called EDM4eic [21]. The EDM4eic data-model is defined in PODIO style. This data-model is a customization of a more generic data-model developed for high energy physics applications, called EDM4hep [22]. In Fig. 5.4, we can notice the elaborated description of the detector, its interfacing with Geant4 and the data-model that dictates the final output format of the simulation outcome.

Figure 5.4: The simulation part itself has multiple components. The DD4hep, detector description interfaces the detector geometry to Geant4 to simulate detector hits. The global data-model is respected in the output of the simulated data, which are being reconstructed.

5.4 Reconstruction

The Reconstruction of the ePIC detector is non trivial. In general, multiple algorithms are interconnected. Such intertwined software requires an efficient and modular structure. The framework needs to be generic so that several algorithms can be added as plugins into the framework, and these plugins can be utilized by other algorithms according to user’s needs. The reconstructed output has to follow the prescribed data-model; therefore, interfacing the EDM4eic into the ePIC reconstruction is also important.

The Reconstruction framework of ePIC software stack is called EICrecon [23]. Its function is to take real or simulated data and reconstruct them extracting physical parameters for later analysis. EICrecon is a framework based on the JLab ANAalysis framework (JANA) [24], an advanced C++ framework for multi-threaded HENP (High Energy and Nuclear Physics) event reconstruction.

The reconstruction of the single photon Cherenkov angle requires knowledge of the detected hit positions, the optical system of the detector, and the track parameters projected onto the Cherenkov radiator surface. Accessing the geometrical description of the dRICH via DD4hep allows the reconstruction algorithm to access the optical parameters and the hit coordinates of the hit SiPM. Meanwhile, the Cherenkov reconstruction algorithm interfaces with the tracking algorithm of EICrecon. ACTS [25] is used for tracking. The Cherenkov angle reconstruction algorithm also communicates with other EICrecon algorithms (for example, digitization).

Our preliminary scheme has now evolved into a fairly complicated diagram. In Fig. 5.5, we see that within EICRecon any algorithm can be interconnected. The interfacing of the primary algorithm (for example, Cherenkov angle reconstruction algorithm) can be done with some secondary algorithms (we call them factories) that can perform certain specific tasks; such as interfacing with data-model, or porting geometry from DD4hep.

The final part is the user analysis of the reconstructed data, where one can generate certain benchmark plots. The benchmark plots can be categorized into different groups: a) physics benchmark, b) reconstruction benchmark, c) detector benchmark. At this point, when we are comfortable with the description of the software stack, let us emphasize that this description is a simplification of complexity. These simplifications, however, do not destroy the global message of the software framework. In Fig. 5.6, we see a more realistic and detailed flowchart of the software used for dRICH simulation in ePIC software framework. For example, we notice that the dRICH geometry itself is embedded in the simulation output file. At the reconstruction level, a dedicated EICrecon factory obtains the geometry from the simulation file. Nonetheless, we understand the excessive level of modularity in the software stack, which requires meticulous care when it comes to debugging or implementing new features.

Figure 5.5: A schematic diagram of the ePIC software stack

It is also important to note that in ePIC dRICH, the true Monte Carlo photons are filtered by implementing a realistic Photon Detection Efficiency (PDE). The filtering occurs at the EICrecon digitized photon class. Furthermore, an additional safety factor (0.7) is added to these surviving photons to ensure conservative estimations of detector performance. The collection of these photons is called digitized hits.

To incorporate the SiPM dark count rates, random hits are added on top of these digitized hits. They are randomly distributed over the sensor surface with user tunable rate and time window. A random time within the time range of the dRICH time response (Chapter 8) is assigned to the noise hits.

5.4.1 Inverse Ray Tracing

We discuss the key features of the algorithm used to reconstruct the single Cherenkov photon angles this subsection. The algorithm is based on Inverse Ray Tracing (IRT). The principle was first introduced by Ypsilantis and Seguinot [26]. In Fig. 5.7, we notice that the spherical mirror focuses the Cherenkov photons emitted uniformly along the particle path in the radiator onto the detector surface, the detected hit position being D . The fact that the photons are focused minimizes the uncertainty due to the unknown emission point. Therefore, as a first approximation, the midpoint of the charged particle inside the radiator can be assumed to be an average emission point (E). If the mirror parameters (Radius R and center O) are

Figure 5.6: dRICH software scheme flowchart in ePIC software framework.

known accurately, one can iteratively estimate the photon vector, for which the incidence angle and the reflected angle on the mirror surface are the same (R). The projection of the photon vector over the track vector gives the Cherenkov angle.

Currently, a C++ code estimates the single photon Cherenkov angle [27]. By using this single photon Cherenkov angle information, an event based chi-square is computed to separate two mass hypotheses in a combinatorial way. The algorithm looks for photon hits in a two sigma corridor, where sigma is the resolution of the measured Cherenkov angle. Thanks to the prompt Cherenkov photons and the excellent timing performance of the photon detectors the images are not only resolved in spatial but also in time coordinates.

5.5 Summary

The ePIC software stack has a multi-layered, interconnected scheme that involves a great deal of care when modifications and optimizations are needed. The DD4hep,

Figure 5.7: Working principle of Inverse Ray Tracing

EICrecon, and IRT are all advanced Object Oriented C++ programs that support multiple inheritance and polymorphism. A software stack as advanced as ePIC, therefore, requires a deep and flawless understanding of the entire workflow. In the following chapters, we will look into the results obtained by writing pieces of code in the core reconstruction software and changing detector parameters at the simulation and reconstruction stages. To ensure meaningful physics results from such a complex software stack, one needs to validate the outcomes by comparing them with first principle calculations and developing analysis scripts that add sufficient redundancy to minimize any error due to software mishandling.

Chapter 6

dRICH performances with different SiPMs parameters

The dRICH detector will use SiPMs to detect Cherenkov photons, as described in Section 4.4. Their characteristics are crucial to the detector performance. In this chapter, the dependence of the PID capability of the dRICH on the choice of SiPM parameters will be discussed.

In the current mechanical and simulation models, the photon detection surface is composed of a matrix of Photon Detection Units (PDUs). Each PDU has 4 (= 2x2) Multi-Pixel Photon Counter (MPPC) elements; each MPPC is formed by an array of 8x8 SiPMs of surface dimension $3 \times 3 \text{mm}^2$, separated by a 0.2 mm gap. The PDUs cover a total area of $5 \times 5 \text{cm}^2$, with a gap of 3 mm between PDUs. This design, and therefore the dead area of the detector, is kept fixed in this study. The Photon Detection Efficiency (PDE) of the SiPMs is another characterizing parameter that has been varied in this study. It is relevant to note that PDE depends on the photon wavelength.

In the simulation environment, the physical design is constructed using DD4hep, described in Chapter 5. The photons that do not hit a SiPM matrix are lost and not stored; at this level, the probability of detecting a photon impinging on the matrix area is 1. At the reconstruction level, the PDE and the Geometrical Fill Factor (GFF) of the matrix are implemented; therefore, the detection probability of each photon is given by the GFF and by the PDE of the detector at the wavelength of the photon.

Different PDEs, corresponding to various SiPMs types, were considered:

- In the current simulation framework, parameters of a SiPMs, produced by Hamamatsu, model number S13361-3050AE-08, with pixel area $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ and a glass epoxy protective window, are in use. They are referred to as the default SiPMs [28].

- SiPMs of the Hamamatsu MPPC S13360 series[29] have a silicon protective window that allows them to detect photons of smaller wavelengths. The performance studies using $50\mu\text{m}$ and $75\mu\text{m}$ pixels will be presented. In the later part of the thesis, these SiPMs will be labeled according to their pixel size, and they will be referred to as the $50\mu\text{m}$ and $75\mu\text{m}$ SiPMs.
- Another SiPM with a quartz window that further extends the PDE in the UV range, which allows detection of photons down to 200 nm , will be labeled as the UV SiPM. It must be pointed out that, while the others are commercially available and tested models, these are novel devices that are less extensively tested, and future production might present different PDEs.

The PDEs were extracted from their respective datasheets and can be seen in Fig. 6.1.

Figure 6.1: PDE for different SiPMs extracted from their datasheet and plotted together. The black vertical line signs the wavelength at which half of the photons produced in the aerogel radiator are absorbed by the acrylic filter described in section 6.1.1

To compare the performances of the detector with different SiPMs, 1 K single particle events were simulated for each momentum and pseudorapidity bin for both pions and kaons. The simulated data were generated in three pseudorapidity bins ($[2.0 \div 2.5]$, $[2.5 \div 3.0]$, $[3.0 \div 3.5]$) and momentum values that reached Cherenkov saturation in the respective radiator; the momentum bins are monochromatic ($\Delta P = 0.1\text{ GeV}/c$).

The PID power has been determined by the number of sigma separations between

a pion and kaon hypothesis; where $\sigma = \frac{\sigma_K + \sigma_\pi}{2}$.

$$N_\sigma = \frac{\langle \theta_K \rangle - \langle \theta_\pi \rangle}{\sigma}$$

where

- $\langle \theta_{K(\pi)} \rangle$ is the mean reconstructed Cherenkov angle for kaons (pions).
- $\sigma_{K(\pi)}$ is the track level Cherenkov angle resolution of kaons (pions). This "ring resolution" is related to the Single Photon Resolution (SPR) $\sigma_\theta : \frac{\sigma_\theta}{\sqrt{NPE}} \oplus C$, and C is a term that includes the uncertainties affecting the reconstructed track.

6.1 Aerogel performance

The aerogel radiator aims to separate pions from kaons in the low momentum range (up to ~ 15 GeV/c). Shifting its upper limit towards a higher momentum value provides the possibility of having a larger overlap with the gas radiator PID range (in the gas radiator, the kaons have an effective threshold ~ 13 GeV/c).

The current aerogel used in the simulation studies has an average refractive index of $n = 1.026$, and it is 4 cm thick. Its more relevant characteristics are presented in Fig. 6.2.

Figure 6.2: Left: Refractive index of the aerogel as a function of wavelength. Right: Mean free path for absorption inside aerogel as versus wavelength (blue curve, left vertical axis) and Probability of survive crossing 2 cm of aerogel, namely half of the radiator length, the average quantity the photons produced in Aerogel have to cross (red curve, right vertical axis).

Implementation of SiPMs with a larger PDE leads to more photons being detected, as can be seen in figure 6.3. However, the photons in the UV spectrum are

affected more by Rayleigh scattering, which worsens the Single Photon Resolution (SPR), as can be seen in figure 6.4. In this figure, it can also be appreciated that 50 μm and 75 μm SiPMs have the same SPR because of their similar detection range. These two factors are counter directional, leading to the presented ring resolution in Fig. 6.5. The default SiPMs have the lowest number of detected photons, but their narrow detection range leads to a better ring resolution compared to the 50 μm and 75 μm SiPMs.

In figure 6.6, the expected number of photons, implementing different SiPMs, was computed using the Frank and Tamm law, they have been compared to cases where the aerogel ring is fully contained in one sector. The estimation takes into account several aspects: wavelength dependency of absorption, PDEs, and reflections. However, it cannot take into account all the factors present in a real simulation and reconstruction, such as the dependency of optical parameters on the impinging angle, polarization states, etc. Nevertheless, these computations are useful to estimate, in the first order, the effects of different parameters and to cross-check the outcome of the reconstruction algorithm. Nevertheless, the consistency between the expected Number of detected photoelectrons (NPE) at saturation and the reconstructed NPE of the simulated data can be seen in table 6.1.

We notice that there is a discrepancy between the computed and reconstructed NPE for the UV graded SiPMs. This discrepancy is understood; the UV photons are subject to larger chromatic aberration and therefore not all of them are included in the nominal ring region defined within the reconstruction algorithm.

SiPM	Computation	Simulation
default	17.7	17.9 ± 0.1
50um	22.4	21.0 ± 0.2
75um	26.9	24.7 ± 0.2
UV	35.9	29.9 ± 0.2

Table 6.1

In figure 6.7, it can be seen that 75 μm and UV lower the PID power of the detector; however, due to the larger detection efficiency, an improvement in the signal-to-noise ratio is expected. This aspect will become particularly important when noise is introduced in the simulation (Chapter 8).

The number of sigma of separation between two particles in a RICH detector should follow:

$$N_\sigma \approx \frac{|m_1^2 - m_2^2|}{2p^2\sigma\sqrt{n^2 - 1}} \quad (6.1)$$

A fit was performed on the $N_\sigma(p)$ curves to estimate the upper detection limit in

different cases using the function:

$$y = [0] \cdot x^{-2} \tag{6.2}$$

A fit, including a second parameter [1], summed with the rest of the function, was tested, but it resulted in always being compatible with 0.

In general, for aerogel, the default SiPMs give the best results. Expanding the detection range in the UV spectrum degrades performance. The worst results are obtained using the 50 μm SiPMs, as their PDE is similar to that of the default SiPM above a wavelength of 300 nm; therefore, the NPE gain in the lower wavelength range is too small to counterbalance the chromatic aberrations.

Figure 6.3: Mean NPE for Cherenkov photons produced in aerogel by pions versus momentum in different pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs.

Figure 6.4: Single photon resolution for Cherenkov photons produced in aerogel by pions versus momentum in different pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs.

Figure 6.5: Ring resolution for Cherenkov photons produced in aerogel by pions versus momentum in different pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs.

Figure 6.6: NPE from the aerogel radiator. Top: Detected NPE from calculation versus momentum using different SiPMs. Bottom: NPE distribution for pions at 15 GeV/c reconstructed with default SiPM.

Figure 6.7: N_σ $\pi - \kappa$ separation in aerogel versus momentum in three pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs.

6.1.1 Acrylic Filter

In the current design, the dRICH mounts a 3 mm thick acrylic filter between the two radiators. This isolates the two radiators and prevents any possible contamination of the aerogel by the perfluoroethane. Its presence leads to reflections and absorption of the photons produced in the aerogel, especially in the UV range, as seen in figure 6.8.

Figure 6.8: Mean free path (blue curve, left vertical axis) and transmittance (red curve, right vertical axis) through the 3 mm thick filter as a function of the photon wavelength. Reflections effects are not considered due to their dependence on the impinging angle.

Figure 6.9: Fractional NPE reduction expressed in percentage at saturation by introducing the filter for the different SiPMs vs pseudorapidity.

Figure 6.10: Expected number of detected photons using different SiPMs with (full lines) and without (dashed lines) the filter.

Figure 6.11: Fractional improvement of single photon resolution expressed in percentage at saturation by introducing the filter for the different SiPMs vs pseudorapidity.

Figure 6.12: N_σ $\pi - \kappa$ separation in aerogel removing the filter versus momentum in three pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs. This plots have to be compared with those presented in Fig. 6.7.

Figure 6.13: Momentum difference (without - with filter) for $3\sigma \pi - \kappa$ separation versus pseudorapidity using different SiPMs.

The loss in the NPE caused by the filter is not negligible, as shown in figures 6.9 and 6.10. At the same time, the presence of the acrylic filter improves the SPR (Fig. 6.11) by filtering photons subject to chromatic aberrations. Nevertheless, the combination of these two effects results in a very modest decrease in PID performance, as illustrated in figures 6.12 and 6.13. The largest worsening effect occurs for the default SiPMs, which not only have a lower number of detected photons but also do not improve the single photon resolution. In figure 6.13, the performance of the default SiPM is clearly separated from the others.

6.2 Gas Performances

The default gas radiator for the dRICH is Hexafluoroethane, C_2F_6 , which has an average refractive index of 1.00086 at STP[16]. In the simulation software, the refractive index curve has been rescaled to describe it at 25°C, Fig. 6.14, and the mean path for absorption is fixed at 30 m over the whole spectrum. The Rayleigh scattering effect in gas is negligible. Furthermore, thanks to its low chromaticity, the gain in the number of detected photons due to higher PDE values in the low wavelength range is not counterbalanced by any degrading effect. Therefore, it is possible to appreciate an improvement in the performance of the detector.

Also, for the gas radiator, the calculated Frank-Tamm curve can be seen in figure 6.15, and the values at saturation are compared with the reconstructed number of photons for an ideal case in table 6.2. In figure 6.16, the number of detected photons using different SiPMs is plotted, while in figure 6.17, it can be seen

that the single photon resolution worsens even for the gas, but by a factor much lower (~ 0.15 mrad(10%) instead of ~ 0.5 mrad(25%)), because only chromaticity contributes to the worsening.

In figure 6.19, the improvement in performance is evident.

Figure 6.14: $n-1$ of C_2F_6 as a function of wavelength.

Figure 6.15: Expected NPE of the gas ring.

SiPM	Expected	Measured
default	21.07	21.3 ± 0.1
50um	28.5	34.7 ± 0.2
75um	34.3	40.5 ± 0.2
UV	52.5	50.0 ± 0.2

Table 6.2

Figure 6.16: Mean NPE in the aerogel ring produced by pions as a function of momentum in different pseudorapidity bins with different SiPMs.

Figure 6.17: Single photon resolution of the aerogel ring produced by pions as a function of momentum in different pseudorapidity bins with different SiPMs.

Figure 6.18: Ring resolution of the aerogel ring produced by pions as a function of momentum in different pseudorapidity bins with different SiPMs.

Figure 6.19: $N_\sigma \pi - \kappa$ separation in gas as a function of momentum in different pseudorapidity bins using different SiPMs.

6.3 Chapter Summary

dRICH is the first RICH counter using SiPMs as photosensors. The PID power of the dRICH using the parameters of different SiPMs; which under consideration for their possible usage in the dRICH, has been investigated. For each SiPM type and for both radiators, the number of detected Cherenkov photons, the resolution of the reconstructed Cherenkov angle, and the maximum momentum that can be reached to obtain a 3σ pion-kaon separation, which is a standard figure of merit used in the literature to qualify RICH counters, have been determined.

Using SiPM with PDE extended in the UV domain, a larger number of Cherenkov photons is detected. The SPR is worsened due to the more marked chromaticity of the UV domain. Nevertheless, the global resolution improves because the larger number of photons overcomes the SPR limitation. The improvement is more marked for the gas radiator, where the advantages of more photons have been fully exploited. The aerogel radiator is followed by an acrylic filter that cuts wavelengths shorter than ~ 280 nm. The filter is required to limit the relevant chromaticity affecting aerogel at lower wavelengths. Therefore, the improvement obtained with the UV extended SiPM is less pronounced. The effect of the filter has been studied in detail.

The number of detected photons can also be increased by using SiPMs with larger pixel sizes ($70 \times 70 \mu\text{m}^2$ versus $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$). The reduced dead area of the SiPM surface that larger pixel sizes offer effectively increases the PDE. A net improvement in PID power is hence observed.

The studies described in this Chapter provide clear guidance for the selection of the SiPMs to be implemented in the dRICH.

Chapter 7

dRICH performance with different mirror parameters

The dRICH is a focusing RICH, as anticipated in Chapter 4. The design includes six spherical mirror sectors that focus the photons on six corresponding detector sectors. The coating of the surfaces determines their reflectance, which is a function of the wavelength. Different reflectance parameters (figure 7.1) were studied to understand their impact on the dRICH performance.

Figure 7.1: The reflectivities curves studied.

The reflectance variation versus photon wavelength is more relevant in the UV range. Therefore, the performance is studied using different SiPMs. Three reflectance cases were studied:

- The default configuration uses a constant value of 0.9 as the reflectance of the mirror across the entire spectrum.
- The reflectance of the LHCb mirrors (figure 7.1).
- The reflectance of the mirrors for the pFRICH (figure 7.1).

Figure 7.2: Relative difference (pFRICH reflectivity - default reflectance) in the number of photons detected in the aerogel radiator for various SiPMs considering the pFRICH parameters.

Figure 7.3: Relative difference (pFRICH reflectivity - default reflectance) in the number of photons detected in the gas radiator for various SiPMs considering the pFRICH parameters.

The pRICH curve is below 0.9 over the whole spectrum, which leads to a loss in NPE with respect to the default configuration, as shown in figures 7.2 and 7.3. For the gas radiator, the effect is larger because, under 300 nm, the reflectance drops to 70%, while the aerogel photons at these wavelengths are absorbed in the filter, as described in section 6.1.1. For the gas radiator, the default SiPMs represent a special case; in fact, they do not detect photons in the region where the reflectance drops; therefore, the impact of different reflectance curves is negligible.

Figure 7.4: Relative difference (LHCb reflectivity - default reflectance) in the number of photons detected in the aerogel radiator for various SiPMs considering the LHCb parameters.

Figure 7.5: Relative difference (LHCb reflectivity - default reflectance) in the number of photons detected in the gas radiator for various SiPMs considering the LHCb parameters.

The LHCb parameters show an increase in the number of photons, figures 7.4 and 7.5, especially for the aerogel, due to the gain in reflectance in the 300 nm ÷ 600 nm range, which is not compensated by the loss under 300 nm. At longer wavelengths, the values were extrapolated with a linear fit, but it is reasonable to think that the real curve would stabilize around 0.85.

Figure 7.6: Difference of the estimated $3\sigma \pi - K$ separation upper limit in momentum for aerogel radiator.

Figure 7.7: Difference of the estimated $3\sigma \pi - K$ separation upper limit in momentum for gas radiator.

The difference in single photon resolution is at the percent level because the detection range does not change. Globally, the performance is similar to that obtained with the default reflectance configuration. This is confirmed in figures 7.6 and 7.7 where the estimated 3σ pions-kaons separation upper limit for the LHCb and the default cases are compared.

The effect on the performance of the aerogel is larger. However, using a wavelength independent 90% reflectivity of the mirror is a reasonable approximation. The available parameterization of the mirror reflectance shows similarities in terms of the number of detected photons and the upper limit of the momentum up to which the dRICH can perform three σ pion kaon separations. In the future, when more sophisticated parameterizations of the dRICH mirror reflectance are available, similar studies can be performed.

7.1 Chapter Summary

The default assumption is that the dRICH mirror has 90% reflectance, independent of the impinging photon wavelength. This preliminary assumption has been compared with two cases of reflectance from existing mirror parameterization. In one of the cases (pfRICH mirrors), moderate, almost negligible degradation in performance is observed. In the second case (LHCb mirrors), some modest performance improvement is observed. No marked effect is evident, confirming that the default configuration is a reasonable approach to adopt until precise data on the reflectance of the dRICH mirrors becomes available.

Chapter 8

dRICH time response

A dedicated simulation study has been performed to determine the time distribution of the collected photons from an event. This study is particularly important for understanding the width of the time window needed by the electronics. In a daily life example, we can imagine it as the shutter time of a camera. On one hand, if the shutter time is too short, we lose our Cherenkov photons of interest; on the other hand, if we open the window for too long, we integrate more intrinsic dark count noise (DCR) from the SiPM, hence limiting the PID performance.

The output of the Geant4 simulation stores the time of the Monte Carlo (MC) photon hits; this time is defined as the moment when the photons end up in the sensitive volume, and the start of the clock is defined as the start of the event in the vertex. Theoretically, we expect that the distribution should be centered around ~ 14 ns. The particles simulated in the events are usually ultra-relativistic ($v \sim c$). The dRICH active volume starts at 1.98 m from the interaction vertex, and it has roughly a 120 cm radiator length. Therefore, a pion of 50 GeV would take ~ 10 ns to reach the end of the radiator. There, the last photon is emitted, which, after reflecting from the mirror surface, roughly travels the radiator length to reach the sensor surface. The photons emitted move at $v = c/n$, where n is the refractive index of the material. In C_2F_6 , it is roughly about 4 ns. Therefore, the photons in the gas arrive at the sensor surface around 14 ns after the start of the event. Given the focusing nature of dRICH, the photons are also focused in time. Therefore, the emission point uncertainty is less relevant. Using a similar argument, one can estimate the arrival time of the photons generated in the aerogel. They arrive at the photo-sensor surface a little later (a few tens of picoseconds) than the gas photons. This is due to path-length considerations. This characteristic will soon be discussed.

As a first step to study the different factors that contribute to the time distribution, 1 K single particle events, at fixed momentum, pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle were simulated. In figure 8.1, the hit map and the corresponding time

distribution for 1 K pions with momentum 11 GeV/c, and at $\eta = 2.0$ are shown. It can be appreciated that there are two main peaks around 14 ns. These peaks correspond to the photons generated in the gas and aerogel, as demonstrated in figure 8.2.

Figure 8.1: Hitmap (left) and detection time distribution (right) of the photons produced simulating 1000 pions at 11 GeV/c, $\eta = 2.0$, and fixed Φ . The hitmap shows only one dRICH sector; more photons are present on other sectors, but they are only background photons because the azimuthal angle was fixed during the simulation so to center the rings on the photosensor surface of a single sector.

The reason behind this separation is due to the different path lengths traveled by the photons. In the aerogel, the photons are emitted at a larger angle, which leads to a longer travel path before reaching at the sensor surface. Considering two photons, one from each radiator, emitted at the radiators interface, the difference in path length can be computed as $\Delta L = 2m \cdot \left[1/\cos(\theta_a) - 1/\cos(\theta_g) \right]$, where θ_g and θ_a are, respectively, the Cherenkov angles in gas and in aerogel with respect to the trajectory after being refracted at the radiators interface.

It can be shown that, at saturation, $\theta_a = \frac{n_g}{\sqrt{1+n_g^2-n_a^2}}$, where n_a, n_g are, respectively, the aerogel and the gas refractive indices. Therefore, using the average refractive index of the radiators, $\Delta L \simeq 5.3$ cm for saturated pions in both radiators, and taking 30 cm/ns as the speed of light, we get a time difference of the order of ~ 0.18 ns, which is in perfect agreement with the distance between the centers of the two peaks.

Figure 8.2: Hitmaps of the photons emitted by 1000 pions at 11 GeV/c, $\eta = 2.0$ and fixed Φ selected applying different time cuts.

The time distribution, as shown in the right panel of Fig. 8.1, has a long tail. The shape of the whole distribution is understood. Most of the generated photons are associated with the primary particle that has been simulated. The peaks are identified in Fig. 8.2 as the following; top: the Cherenkov photons generated in the gas radiator; middle: the Cherenkov photons generated in the aerogel radiator; bottom: mostly Rayleigh scattered photons distributed in the same sector as the ring photons and those scattered to off-sector.

In figure 8.3, four different components of the time distribution are demonstrated. Apart from Cherenkov photons generated by the primary pion, a large background is generated by secondary electrons. These secondary electrons are generated by the interaction of pions with different detector materials. Additionally, there is a finite probability of the pion decaying into a muon. This has also been observed. Moreover, few unstable charged particles are also generated and the photons associated with these particles can also be seen. These photons in the broad tail may have a different generation mechanism, such as Scintillation. In figure 8.4 the hit maps of the different components are presented.

Figure 8.3: Different components of the time distribution of the photons produced simulating 1000 pions at 11 GeV/c, $\eta = 2.0$ and fixed Φ .

In figure 8.5, it is possible to notice the presence of more structures in the main peak of the distributions. Each one of the peaks is a superposition of two different nearby peaks. This can be understood from fig 8.6, where a zoomed hit map is presented, and the color scale along the z-axis represents the detection time of the photons. The photons that are closer to the beam pipe arrive at the sensor earlier compared to the photons that are further away.

Furthermore, the appearance of the structure inside the peak is not the same for all pseudorapidity values. The focusing of the dRICH optics ensures that the most optimized pseudorapidity region is between 2.5 to 3.5; as a consequence, the photons are subject to less path length variation in the lower pseudorapidity region. Therefore, the photons are extremely sensitive to the slightest change in the path length in the higher pseudorapidity regions.

Figure 8.4: Hitmaps of the photons emitted by different type of particles.

The distribution shape changes also with momentum, due to the different emission angles; and it also changes if the ring is full contained in a single sector or get split and distributed into more than one sectors. To determine the total event time distribution presented in figure 8.7 different cases were considered altogether.

It is not sufficient to determine a realistic time distribution using single particle events. Realistic physics events might give rise to complex events and dominate the shape of the time distribution. In particular, Weak decays can take relatively longer time, which retards the detection of the photons, in fig 8.8 a,b two single particle events are compared, and multiparticle events can have wider distributions as seen in figure 8.8 c. For this reason hepmc files generated with Pythia8 of pe^- DIS events were used as input for the simulation environment. So far, in this study, the experimental resolution of the time information is not folded in. It is expected that the TDC in the dRICH read-out chain has $\sigma \sim 150$ ps; therefore, the time distribution obtained by the simulation has to be folded with a gaussian distribution with this standard deviation to simulate the impact of the experimental resolution.

Figure 8.5: Time distributions for 1000 pions at 50 GeV/c, fixed Φ and different pseudorapidities.

Figure 8.6: Hitmap of the gas ring for 1000 pions at $p = 50$ GeV/c, $\eta = 3.0$

Figure 8.7: Time distribution of all the photons emitted by pions, kaons, electrons and protons at $p \in 5, 19, 50$ GeV/c and $\eta \in [1.5; 3.5]$. The vertical axis is in arbitrary units.

Figure 8.8: Two different DIS event time distributions. Left: a single particle event; Right: a multi-particle event.

The result leads to a distribution of ~ 3 ns wide in which all the structures are completely diluted as shown in fig8.10.

Already from the single particle events, it was clear that the tail of the distribution is populated by photons generated either by secondary particles or by scattered

Figure 8.9: Time distribution of the Cherenkov photons emitted by the produced particles of 50 pe collisions.

Figure 8.10: Time distribution seen in fig8.9, but the values are convoluted with a gaussian to replicate the smearing.

photons, which fall far from the ring, or by a combination of both. Currently, the photons that are associated to a reconstructed ring have not been studied. In future, dedicated studies will be needed to determine the time distribution of the reconstructed photons. From this initial investigation, we can conclude that in order to collect all the photons of an event, a time window of, at least, 3 ns is

needed. In section 8.1 the effects of a white background, which simulates the dark count rate of the SiPMs has been studied using 3 ns time window as a reference time window for the dRICH.

8.1 Impact of noise on the performance

The noise in a RICH detector consist of hits that are not generated by the charged particle undergoing Cherenkov effect. Such hits blur the image, and therefore, affect the SPR. One important background contribution is the dark count of the SiPMs. It is expected that, at maximum radiation damage, the noise rate per pixel will be of the order of ~ 300 kHz. Assuming a 3 ns time window, and considering the whole instrumented photosensor surface, ~ 300 expected dark noise hits per event are expected.

To simulate this effect, white noise is injected into the photosensor surface. The total amount of noise hits for the event is generated with a Poisson statistics centered around the expected number of dark count hits. Then, a number of SiPMs corresponding to the total amount of noise hits is randomly selected, one by one, and a digitized hit is generated for those SiPMs. An information related to the time of these hits is associated, assuming a random distribution within this 3 ns window.

It is expected that the aerogel ring will be affected more than the gas ring by the inclusion of the noise. The amount of noise hits is proportional to the circumference of ring. Therefore, the aerogel having a ring radius 5 to 7 times larger than the gas one, and having comparable number of signal photons suffer the largest signal to noise degradation. The number of noise hits that are expected to appear with the aerogel ring region can be computed by estimating the number of SiPMs included in a ring. At saturation the radius of the ring is about 230 mrad, with around ± 2 mrad based on SPR, and for a ring fully contained on a sector, provides the number of SiPMs in the ring is around 550. Therefore, we expect ~ 0.5 dark noise hits per reconstructed ring. This preliminary evaluation has been confirmed by some dedicated simulation studies.

In figure 8.11 it can be appreciated that the actual difference is of the predicted order of magnitude, while in figure 8.12 it is possible to see that the amount of noise hits associated with the track increases linearly with the amount of generated noise. This also confirms the validity of our approach. The N_σ curve, after the noise injection, is shown in figure 8.13. The presence of the dark noise affects the performance of the detector differently based on the type of the SiPMs that are used, as seen in figure 8.14. As already predicted, the default SiPMs are less robust because of a smaller number of photons is detected, resulting in a bigger effect and a N_σ curve fully compatible with the UV and 75um cases.

Figure 8.11: NPE associated to the aerogel ring for 1000 single particle events with and without injecting noise. The particles are π at 13 GeV/c in the range $\eta \in [2.0 : 2.5]$.

Figure 8.12: Increment in number of reconstructed hits in the aerogel ring for 1000 pions at 15 GeV/c when injecting different noise rates.

Figure 8.13: N_σ separation curve for aerogel when dark count noise at 300 kHz is injected.

Figure 8.14: Momentum difference (without - with injecting noise) for $3\sigma \pi - \kappa$ separation versus pseudorapidity using different SiPMs.

8.2 Chapter Summary

In this Chapter, for the first time, the dRICH time response is addressed. At present, the digitization in the ePIC software stack does not simulate the smearing of the time information introduced by the sensor response and the read-out electronics. Therefore, the studies are performed with the generated time information, which provides the time the Cherenkov photons hit the photosensors.

The simulation studies indicate that the distribution of the Cherenkov photon arrival time extends over a window of 3 ns. The main peaks due to Cherenkov photons from gas and aerogel with minimum path length are separated by less than ~ 200 ps.

The impact of the smearing introduced by the sensor and the electronics is approach as first order approximation by folding the time distribution with a gaussian with standard deviation of 150 ps, which is the time resolution expected from the TDCs implemented in the read-out front-end ASIC coupled to the dRICH photosensors. As expected, the fine structure of the time distribution is fully smeared; f.i., the two main peaks produced by the Cherenkov photons from gas and aerogel are merged in a single peak. The global time window of the time distribution remains substantially unchanged.

Including the effect of the SiPM dark noise does not change the picture in a substantial way causing a very limited reduction of the dRICH PID power. This performance decrease is more limited when SiPM with extended PDE ranges are

used thanks to the larger number of detected Cherenkov photons, which enhance the signal over noise ratio.

The relevance of this exercise is two fold:

- it provides a first indication of the opening time of the readout gate;
- it suggest the time window to be used for effective image reconstruction in the dRICH, this being a key parameter for data reduction in a triggerless experiment as ePIC.

Chapter 9

Lower limit of the momentum range for effective particle identification with the dRICH

A dedicated exercise was performed to determine the lower limit for effective PID using the dRICH. The momentum threshold for the Cherenkov effect depends on the mass M of the particle and the refractive index n of the radiator. The momentum threshold grows with the mass of the particle and decreases for increasing refractive index: $p_{\text{th}} = \frac{M}{\sqrt{n^2 - 1}}$. In the dRICH, PID at low momenta is obtained using the aerogel radiator. The hadrons with smaller mass are pions, for which the threshold of the Cherenkov effect in aerogel is $p_{\text{th}, \pi} \sim 0.6 \text{ GeV}/c$. It is important to notice that, at threshold, the expected number of Cherenkov photons is zero, as discussed in section 4.2. It is therefore evident that the effective threshold of a counter based on the Cherenkov effect is higher than the physical threshold. In the following we report about a first exercise aiming to determine the effective momentum threshold of the dRICH.

We have introduced a recipe to determine the effective lower limit. We use pions as reference particle specie. We require a minimum number of Cherenkov photons associated to the pion in the reconstruction process and set the momentum threshold at the momentum value for which in 90% of the cases the number of reconstructed photons associated to the pion is larger than the fixed minimum.

For this exercise, single pions were generated uniformly over the phase-space:

$(p, \eta, \Phi) \in [0.8 \div 2.5] \text{GeV}/c \times [1.9 \div 3.3] \times [-\frac{\pi}{6} \div \frac{\pi}{2}]$. In figure 9.1 a frontal view of the detector is presented showing the azimuthal angle range used.

Figure 9.1: dRICH photosensors frontal view: the azimuthal angle range considered in our study is shown; it ranges between $-\pi/6$ and $\pi/2$.

Figure 9.2: Number of reconstructed photons per track versus particle momentum.

The number of generated photons depends on the momentum as described by the Frank-Tamm law. The number of detected photons depends on the sensor

characteristics, the radiator transparency and the mirror reflectance. It depends on the pseudorapidity and the azimuthal angle of the emitted particle too because of the geometrical effects which modulates the acceptance of the emitted photons. In figure 9.3 the number of reconstructed photons per particle in our exercise is plotted versus particle momentum.

The number of detected photons in each bin (Φ, η) bin is shown in figure 9.3. The modulation in pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle are evident. At higher pseudorapidities part of the aerogel ring is lost because of the beam pipe shadow. In Φ the profile shows different peaks, where the center of the detector sectors sits, and valleys, at the border of two sectors. In fact, the photon acceptance is more limited for trajectories not hearting dRICH sector centers.

Figure 9.3: Average number of reconstructed photons per track versus pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle.

This modulation is reflected on the momentum threshold because, in different pseudorapidity-azimuthal angle bins, the average number of photons is different.

In an ideal case the number of detected photons should follow a Poissonian distribution centered on an expected number which depends on the momentum of the particle and all the efficiency which reduce the number of detected hits. We notice that a non negligible number of empty event (between 5% and 10% according to the different kinematic regions) is present at all momenta. This empty events are generated by non-reconstructed rings due to a too limited number of reconstructed photons and to the efficiency of the current reconstruction algorithm. We take into account also the empty events, which lower the mean value of the detected photons accepted by the reconstruction.

The number of hits necessary to identify a passing particle will strongly depends

on the noise, which is not considered for this study. Therefore, two possible threshold were studied. It was required that at least 90% of the events in the bin present more than 5 (or 7) associated hits. The results are presented in figures 9.4 and 9.5.

Figure 9.4: Momentum threshold versus pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle requiring at least 5 reconstructed photons per track in 90% of the events.

Figure 9.5: Momentum threshold versus pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle requiring at least 7 reconstructed photons per track in 90% of the events.

9.1 Chapter Summary

An initial study dedicated to determine the effective lower limit for PID in the dRICH is reported.

The result indicates that there is a clear dependence on two kinematic parameters, both related to Cherenkov photon acceptance. At larger and larger pseudorapidity more and more photons are screened by the beam pipe resulting in a lower limit for effective PID as high as ~ 1.3 GeV/c and larger than 2 GeV/c setting the minimum number of reconstructed photon for 90% of the pions at 5 and 7, respectively. A modulation in the azimuthal angle is clearly visible, which increases the momentum lower limit for effective PID for pions with trajectories pointing between two dRICH sectors. These initial result requires further extension in order to suggest geometrical adjustments to optimize the dRICH response.

Chapter 10

Conclusions

The original simulation studies reported in this thesis are integral part of the ongoing effort aiming at the validation and design optimization of the dual radiator Ring Imaging Cherenkov counter (dRICH) of the ePIC experiment at the US Electron-Ion Collider (EIC).

The activity has been accompanied by approaching the EIC physics scope, the general design of the ePIC experiment and by the understanding and familiarization with the extended and complex software stack of the ePIC experiment. The last element is mandatory to perform dRICH detector studies by simulation techniques, where also modifications and new implementations in the software domain are needed.

The highlights of the results obtained by the student are recalled in the following.

- The dRICH performance using Silicon PhotoMultipliers (SiPM) with different characteristics has been studied. The increased PID power by adopting SiPMs with UV-extended sensitivity range and with large pixel size has clearly emerged.
- The dRICH performance using mirrors with different reflectance has been studied to understand the criticality of this parameter, which will be precisely known only after an extended prototyping campaign by the producer. Using reflectance curves from existing mirrors used in other experimental efforts no major performance variation has been observed, relaxing the uncertainty level coming from the lack of an exact prediction about the mirror properties.
- For the first time the dRICH time response has been studied and the time distribution has been obtained. This assessment is of great relevance. In fact, it impacts on the signal over noise ratio that can be obtained applying data selection based on timing and dictates the time gate of the read-out electronics, therefore impacting on the data flow in the electronic read-out chain.

- An initial study of the lower limit of the momentum range for effective particle identification with the dRICH has been performed. The effective lower limit is conditioned by the Cherenkov photon acceptance with modulations observed versus pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle of the incoming particle. This study opens the way to the next steps where the noise affecting the dRICH response have to be included.

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Bibliography

- [1] *An Assessment of U.S.-Based Electron-Ion Collider Science*. National Academies Press, Sept. 2018. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17226/25171>.
- [2] A. Accardi et al. «Electron Ion Collider: The Next QCD Frontier - Understanding the glue that binds us all». In: *BNL-98815-2012-JA; JLAB-PHY-12-1652* (Dec. 2012). URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1212.1701.pdf>.
- [3] R Abdul Khalek et al. «Science Requirements and Detector Concepts for the Electron-Ion Collider: EIC Yellow Report». In: *Nuclear Physics A* 1026 (2022), p. 122447. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0375947422000677>.
- [4] Kaoru Hagiwara et al. «Review of Particle Physics: Particle data group». In: *Physical Review D-Particles, Fields, Gravitation and Cosmology* 66.1 I (2002), pp. 100011–10001958.
- [5] Yuri L Dokshitzer. «Calculation of the structure functions for deep inelastic scattering and $e^+ e^-$ annihilation by perturbation theory in quantum chromodynamics». In: *Zh. Eksp. Teor. Fiz* 73 (1977), p. 1216.
- [6] Vladimir Naumovich Gribov and Lev N Lipatov. *DEEP INELASTIC ep-SCATTERING IN A PERTURBATION THEORY*. Tech. rep. Inst. of Nuclear Physics, Leningrad, 1972.
- [7] Guido Altarelli and Giorgio Parisi. «Asymptotic freedom in parton language». In: *Nuclear Physics B* 126.2 (1977), pp. 298–318.
- [8] Bernd A Kniehl, Gustav Kramer, and Björn Pötter. «Testing the universality of fragmentation functions». In: *Nuclear Physics B* 597.1-3 (2001), pp. 337–369.
- [9] G.D. Alexeev et al. «Multiplicities of positive and negative pions, kaons, and unidentified hadrons from deep-inelastic scattering of muons off a liquid hydrogen target». In: *PHYSICAL REVIEW D* (2025), p. 012002.
- [10] Elke C. Aschenauer, and others. «Semi-inclusive deep-inelastic scattering, parton distributions, and fragmentation functions at a future electron-ion collider». In: *PHYSICAL REVIEW D* 99 (2019), p. 094004.

- [11] *The ePIC Collaboration*. URL: <https://www.bnl.gov/eic/epic.php>.
- [12] *ALICE ITS3*. URL: https://alice-collaboration.web.cern.ch/menu_proj_items/ITS-3.
- [13] Eugenio Nappi. «Advances in charged particle identification techniques». In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 628.1 (2011), pp. 1–8.
- [14] PA Čerenkov. «Visible radiation produced by electrons moving in a medium with velocities exceeding that of light». In: *Physical Review* 52.4 (1937), p. 378.
- [15] Arthur Roberts. «A novel mass-sensitive image-dissecting Cherenkov detector». In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods* 99.3 (1972), pp. 589–598.
- [16] R. Abjean, A. Bideau-Mehu, and Y. Guern. «Refractive index of hexafluoroethane (C₂F₆) in the 300-150 nm wavelength range». In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 354.2 (1995), pp. 417–418. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0168900294010064>.
- [17] N. Rubini et al. «The SiPM readout plane for the ePIC-dRICH detector at the EIC: Overview and beam test results». In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 1082 (2026), p. 170890. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900225006928>.
- [18] *Detector Description Toolkit for High Energy Physics*. URL: <https://dd4hep.web.cern.ch/dd4hep/>.
- [19] Rene Brun and Fons Rademakers. «ROOT - An Object Oriented Data Analysis Framework». In: *NIMA* 389 (1997), pp. 81–86.
- [20] S. Agostinelli et al. «Geant4—a simulation toolkit». In: *NIMA* 506.3 (2003), pp. 250–303.
- [21] *EDM4eic - EIC data model*. URL: <https://eic.github.io/EDM4eic/>.
- [22] *EDM4hep: A generic event data model for future HEP collider experiments*. URL: <https://github.com/title4hep/EDM4hep>.
- [23] *EICrecon: JANA based reconstruction for the EPIC detector*. URL: <https://eicrecon.epic-eic.org/#/>.
- [24] *JANA2: Modern C++ Reconstruction framework in Nuclear and High Energy Physics*. URL: <https://jeffersonlab.github.io/JANA2/#/?id=jana2>.
- [25] *ACTS Common Tracking Software*. URL: https://acts.readthedocs.io/en/latest/getting_started.html.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [26] T. Ypsilantis and J. Seguinot. «Theory of ring imaging Cherenkov counters». In: *353* (1994), 30–51.
- [27] *IRT:Indirect Ray Tracing code for ATHENA event reconstruction*. URL: <https://github.com/eic/irt>.
- [28] D.S. Bhattacharya, C. Chatterjee and others. «Simulation studies related to the particle identification by the forward and backward RICH detectors at Electron Ion Collider». In: *NIMA* 1056 (2023), p. 168591.
- [29] *HAMAMATUS MPPC (Multi-Pixel Photon Counter) S13360 series*. URL: https://www.hamamatsu.com/content/dam/hamamatsu-photonics/sites/documents/99_SALES_LIBRARY/ssd/s13360_series_kapd1052e.pdf.